

From Eco-Anxiety to Employee (Dis)Engagement:
a Quantitative Study in Private Companies

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Abstract

As climate change intensifies, eco-anxiety—a stress response to environmental degradation—has become a growing threat to employee engagement in private companies. This study examined how psychological, organizational, and socio-environmental factors linked to eco-anxiety affect engagement, with implications for well-being, performance, and retention.

Grounded in Kahn’s engagement theory, the transactional model of stress, and the job demands-resources model, this quantitative, non-experimental, correlational, cross-sectional study surveyed 182 private-sector employees across 17 countries who self-identified as experiencing eco-anxiety. The online questionnaire captured demographic data and twelve proxy factors across the psychological, organizational, and socio-environmental domains.

Descriptive and inferential statistics revealed that ten of twelve hypotheses were supported.

Psychological, organizational, and socio-environmental factors each showed significant associations with reduced employee engagement.

The study concludes that eco-anxiety is a multidimensional workplace stressor with significant organizational and policy implications. It led to the development of the eco-anxiety and workplace (dis)engagement (EWD) framework, which provides a conceptual basis for understanding and addressing these effects. Based on this framework, the study offers recommendations for targeted HR and leadership strategies to help mitigate the impact of eco-anxiety on employee engagement. The study’s Eurocentric, female, and sustainability-focused sample limits generalizability; future research should validate the EWD framework and examine demographic and organizational influences on engagement.

Keywords: climate anxiety, climate change, eco-anxiety, employee engagement, EWD framework, organizations, well-being

Dedication

This dissertation is lovingly dedicated to:

To my daughter, Nora Petetin, who was 8 years old when I finished this journey but wise far beyond her years. Nora, you have been the most amazing support a mother could dream of: my brainstorming partner, and my most creative cheerleader. Your drawings, positive messages on my whiteboard before long research nights, and even the "pre-diplomas" you awarded me when I needed a boost have kept me going. More than anyone, you remind me why I chose to write this dissertation in the field of sustainability: because our generation must act now so yours can thrive. My hope is to be a good ancestor, doing my part to build a better world for you and your friends.

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And to all the future generations and every person striving to make the world better. Every action matters, no matter how small. This work is my contribution—to help businesses see that climate change isn't just an environmental issue, it's a human one that directly impacts employees and society. Let's not overlook that. Let's act.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

The growing threat of climate change is not only an environmental crisis but also a psychological one. Employees are increasingly experiencing eco-anxiety and its long-term consequences, expecting businesses to take meaningful action (de Lange et al., 2022). Corporate social responsibility (CSR) policies are playing an increasingly important role in job selection, as employees seek companies that show genuine commitment to environmental and social responsibility (Wang & Chen, 2022). When employees perceive strong CSR efforts, they tend to experience greater job satisfaction and engagement (Farid et al., 2019). However, skepticism remains, as many workers feel there is a gap between what companies promise and what they actually implement (Latif et al., 2022). Surveys in France, the United States and United Kingdom indicate that half of individuals would consider leaving a company if it does not align with their values, and one-third of individuals aged 18 to 24 have already left for this reason (2023 Net Positive Employee Barometer, 2023; Humacap, 2025). Employees increasingly express frustration with company values and missions, showing a preference for environmentally responsible employers (Hicklenton et al., 2021; Spanjol et al., 2014). They also struggle to thrive in roles that lack significance, engagement, and alignment with their environmental values.

Nowadays, businesses are expected to act as good ancestors for future generations (Krznaric, 2020). Traditional employee engagement strategies may no longer suffice. Instead, organizations could gain to cultivate a deeper, more meaningful connection. By aligning corporate objectives and values with workforce concerns, companies can address eco-anxiety, build resilience, and drive sustainable business outcomes (Lu et al., 2023). This alignment is particularly urgent as eco-anxiety continues to rise, posing a direct threat to workforce engagement and organizational adaptability (de Lange et al., 2022). Clayton et al. (2017) define

eco-anxiety as a “chronic fear of environmental doom” (p. 68), arising from anticipated climate-related suffering and destruction. The 2021 *Lancet planetary health* study highlighted the growing connections between climate change, mental health, and emotional well-being (Hickman et al., 2021). In 2023, research found that 42.8% of individuals across 25 European countries experience some level of eco-anxiety (Niedzwiedz & Katikireddi, 2023). With climate change becoming a psychological burden, its impact on the workforce cannot be ignored. Employee engagement is a fundamental driver of retention, motivation, and organizational performance (Harter et al., 2002; Harter et al., 2003), yet rising climate-related distress threatens to undermine this foundation.

Human activities have profoundly altered Earth's ecosystems (IPCC, 2022). Crossing the critical 1.5°C global warming threshold is expected to trigger severe consequences, including biodiversity loss, food and water shortages, ecosystem collapse, and widespread physical and mental health crises (Gidden et al., 2023; IPCC, 2022). The increasing media coverage of climate change has further intensified public awareness and distress, making it increasingly difficult for individuals to ignore these challenges (Loll et al., 2023; Ogunbode et al., 2022). Research suggests that eco-anxiety significantly affects mental health, contributing to stress, depression, and existential concerns (Hickman et al., 2021; Niedzwiedz & Katikireddi, 2023). Despite these growing concerns, its implications for workplace engagement and organizational well-being remain underexplored.

In academic literature, the terms "eco-anxiety" and "climate anxiety" are often used interchangeably (Pihkala, 2020). Emerging research recognizes eco-anxiety as a growing workplace concern (Ayassamy et al., 2024; Joshua et al., 2022). Joshua et al. (2022) suggest that higher levels of eco-anxiety may weaken the relationship between green workplace attributes and

voluntary pro-environmental behaviors. In addition, other findings indicate that employees experiencing strong climate-related emotions are more likely to engage in sustainability-driven workplace behaviors (Ágoston et al., 2024; Clayton & Karazsia, 2020; Innocenti et al., 2023). However, for some individuals, these emotions may instead result in eco-paralysis, diminishing their willingness to engage in initiatives (Innocenti et al., 2023). These insights highlight the need for deeper investigation into the psychological mechanisms linking eco-anxiety and workplace engagement.

Despite mounting evidence that eco-anxiety is a significant mental health concern, its impact on workplace motivation, engagement, and productivity remains largely unexamined (Ayassamy et al., 2024; Brooks & Greenberg, 2022). While employee engagement has long been established as a key determinant of organizational performance and well-being, its intersection with climate-related psychological distress remains an underexplored area of research (Harter et al., 2002; Harter et al., 2003). As of 2024, only one study has specifically examined how organizations can address eco-anxiety in the workplace (Ayassamy et al., 2024), highlighting a significant gap in the literature.

Employee engagement itself is a multifaceted concept, encompassing work engagement, job engagement, and general engagement (Lee et al., 2017; Saks & Gruman, 2014). Kahn (1990) defines work engagement as the degree to which employees express themselves physically, cognitively, and emotionally in their roles. Given the rising prevalence of eco-anxiety, understanding its influence on work engagement is essential for shaping effective HR strategies.

Statement of the Problem

The problem to be addressed by this research is the negative impact of eco-anxiety on employee engagement in the workplace (Ayassamy et al., 2024; Brooks & Greenberg, 2022).

Eco-anxiety is prevalent among Generation Z (Niedziedz & Katikireddi, 2023), born between the mid-1990s and early 2010s, who will soon represent a significant share of the global workforce (Bloomgarden, 2022). The environmental distress on Generation Z's mental health emphasizes the urgent need for organizations to acknowledge and address eco-anxiety in their management practices. Given that engaged employees drive business success (Macey & Schneider, 2008), it is essential to consider how they can sustain engagement and performance when faced with climate-related fears.

Neglecting mental health concerns, such as eco-anxiety, can lead to significant organizational and economic consequences. The World Health Organization (WHO) defines mental health as a state of well-being that enables individuals to manage challenges, recognize their potential, work productively, and contribute to their communities (WHO, 2024a). Climate-related psychological distress is increasingly recognized as a global public health crisis (Cianconi et al., 2023). WHO estimates that depression and anxiety contribute to 12 billion lost workdays annually, costing the global economy \$1 trillion in productivity losses (WHO, 2024b). Poor mental health in the workplace correlates with increased absenteeism and disengagement (Campion, 2013).

Eco-anxiety is emerging as a widespread concern across all working-age groups, threatening both employee well-being and company productivity (Cosh et al., 2024). Research by Harter et al. (2003) confirms that employees who feel psychologically well perform better, benefiting both themselves and their organizations. Despite employee engagement's well-documented role in business sustainability (Macey & Schneider, 2008), a significant gap remains in empirical research on its relationship with eco-anxiety. Given the pivotal role of engagement

in organizational success, it is crucial to understand how eco-anxiety impacts workforce motivation.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this quantitative, non-experimental, correlational, cross-sectional study is to identify how eco-anxiety contributes to lowering employee engagement in private companies. Specifically, this study investigates eco-anxiety as the independent variable (predictor) and employee engagement as the dependent variable (outcome). A questionnaire was developed to act as the instrument of data collection and was made available online via SurveyMonkey (SurveyMonkey, n.d.). Participants were required to be 18 years or older, experiencing some level of eco-anxiety, and currently employed by a private company. For the present study, the minimum required sample size of 138 participants was computed using an a-priori power analysis by the G*Power 3.1.9.7 software (Faul et al., 2007, 2009) at 0.95 power and 0.05 alpha. The analysis employed the exact test family, with the statistical test specified as the bivariate normal model for correlation. Recruitment was done through social media platforms, including Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn and Slack. The participation was voluntary and anonymous. The collected data were analyzed using SPSS version 29 software (IBM, 2024), with both descriptive and inferential statistics applied to address the study's hypotheses and research questions.

Theoretical Framework

Drawing on established theories and empirical research, I examined how eco-anxiety adversely affects employee engagement in private companies. The study's framework integrates three key theories: Kahn's engagement theory (1990), the transactional model of stress (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984), and the job demands-resources (JD-R) model (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007). Together, these theories provide a comprehensive lens to understand eco-anxiety's impact on engagement.

Employee motivation has been widely studied (Alderfer, 1969; Herzberg et al., 1959; Maslow, 1943), yet there is little consensus on the definition of employee engagement (Lee et al., 2017; Saks & Gruman, 2014). This study adopts Kahn's (1990) definition of work engagement as "the harnessing of organization members' selves to their work roles; in engagement, people employ and express themselves physically, cognitively, and emotionally during role performances" (p. 694). Kahn's multifaceted view emphasizes that meaningfulness, safety, and availability are crucial psychological conditions for engagement. In the context of eco-anxiety, overwhelming environmental challenges may undermine these conditions by inducing feelings of powerlessness.

Building on early stress research, the transactional model of stress (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984) marked a shift from earlier theories, such as Selye's (1956) focus on physiological responses to a more nuanced understanding that highlights cognitive appraisal. This model posits that individuals first evaluate (primary appraisal) whether a stressor poses a threat and then assess (secondary appraisal) their ability to cope with it. In this study, eco-anxiety is conceptualized as an environmental stressor that triggers these appraisal processes. When perceived as overwhelming, eco-anxiety may diminish work engagement; however, adequate coping resources could buffer its negative effects.

Complementing this view, the JD-R model (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007) provides insights into how job demands and resources interact to influence employee outcomes. Rooted in earlier frameworks like Karasek's demand-control model (1979) and Siegrist's effort-reward imbalance model (1996), the JD-R model allows framing eco-anxiety as an emergent job demand that can exacerbate stress and lead to disengagement if not balanced by sufficient resources. Conversely, organizational factors, including company purpose and employee green behavior, may act as job resources that mitigate the negative impact of eco-anxiety.

Building on Miles et al. (2014), I developed a theoretical framework (Figure 1) that illustrates the relationships among key study concepts and the three key theories forming the theoretical foundation of my study. In this model, eco-anxiety functions as a job demand that triggers stress responses per the transactional model of stress (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984), potentially jeopardizing the core psychological conditions for employee engagement: meaningfulness, safety, and availability identified by Kahn (1990). The lack of job resources could contribute to the negative effect in line with the JD-R framework (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007). The psychological, organizational and socio-environmental factors could act as job resources.

Figure 1 *Theoretical Framework*

The psychological factors encompass: lack of control, cognitive dissonance, emotional exhaustion, chronic stress, and low well-being. The lack of control refers to feelings of personal powerlessness when confronting large-scale ecological crises (Hickman et al., 2021; Pihkala,

2020). Cognitive dissonance describes the psychological discomfort that arises when environmental awareness conflicts with unsustainable behaviors (Festinger, 1957; Gifford, 2011). Emotional exhaustion relates to the absence of adequate emotional support in the workplace (Pihkala, 2020). Chronic stress refers to persistent mental health difficulties caused by prolonged exposure to climate-related stressors (Hickman et al., 2021). Low well-being describes the negative condition that individuals and societies can experience (World Health Organization, 2022).

On the other hand, the identified organizational factors include lack of corporate sustainability initiatives, company purpose, employee green behavior, and perceived lack of leadership support. Lack of corporate sustainability initiatives refers to the absence of meaningful actions addressing social and environmental responsibility (Glavas & Kelley, 2014). Company purpose reflects the organization's ambition to drive positive change while providing employees with a strong sense of meaning and significance (Quinn & Thakor, 2018). Employee green behaviors are measurable actions by employees that contribute to environmental sustainability goals in the workplace (Ones & Dilchert, 2012). Perceived lack of leadership support refers to the employee perception that leaders are not committed to or do not actively promote sustainability efforts (Robertson & Barling, 2017).

Finally, the socio-economic factors include media exposure, uncertainty regarding environmental regulations, and perceived environmental regulatory and market pressure. Media exposure refers to the stress caused by alarming media coverage of environmental issues (Niedziedz & Katikireddi, 2023). Uncertainty regarding environmental regulations refers to unpredictable policies that reduce environmental concern (Lu, 2024). Perceived environmental regulatory and market pressure refers to institutional forces, such as regulations and market

expectations, that influence stakeholders' engagement in sustainability efforts (Bansal & Roth, 2000).

Nature of the Study

In this study, I embrace Deweyan pragmatism for its capacity to offer valuable insights when navigating contemporary challenges (Brown, 2009). Guided by this instrumentalist perspective, a quantitative methodology was selected to prioritize measurable outcomes, utilize statistical analyses of numerical data, and test hypotheses (Yilmaz, 2013). This approach aligns with the study's goal of examining factors influencing the negative impact of eco-anxiety on employee engagement, thereby enabling hypothesis testing about these relationships.

This study employs a correlational, non-experimental, and cross-sectional design to align with its research objectives. The primary goal of a correlational design is to examine relationships between variables without manipulation (Harkiolakis, 2021). A non-experimental approach was chosen to observe the natural association between eco-anxiety and employee engagement, rather than establish causality or apply interventions. Since the study captures these associations at a single point in time, the cross-sectional design provides a 'snapshot' of the phenomenon, allowing for data interpretation within a specific timeframe (Gray, 2022).

The targeted population for this study is private-sector employees. Inclusion criteria required participants to be (a) currently employed, (b) at least 18 years old, (c) experiencing some level of eco-anxiety, (d) working in the private sector. As eco-anxiety is shaped by cultural factors and climate change impacts regions at varying rates (Cosh et al., 2024), the decision was made to include professionals regardless of their country of residence. Research on cross-cultural perspectives in employee engagement is also limited, yet such insights could significantly benefit multinational organizations (Awasthi et al., 2025). An a priori power analysis using G*Power

3.1.9.7 (Faul et al., 2007, 2009) determined that a minimum sample of 138 participants (at 95% power and a 0.05 alpha level) was necessary. The analysis used an exact test framework, employing the bivariate normal model as the chosen statistical test for correlation.

To recruit participants, the study used a non-probabilistic purposive sampling method. This approach helps researchers target specific demographic characteristics while expanding the participant pool through referrals (Harkiolakis, 2021). Participants were intentionally selected based on predefined inclusion criteria, and qualified individuals were encouraged to refer others (snowball sampling). Participants were recruited through my professional network and by promoting a call for participation in social media networks (Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, Slack).

A self-administered questionnaire was developed to serve as the instrument of data collection using SurveyMonkey (SurveyMonkey, n.d.). Several measures were implemented to ensure the validity of the questionnaire. Internal validity was strengthened by including multiple question sets related to the same construct. Content validity was addressed through an expert review, conducted by a panel of professionals with 5–10 years of experience in quantitative research and human resources (Harkiolakis, 2021). After the panel approved the questionnaire, a pilot study was conducted to assess its effectiveness and further confirm criterion-based validity (Gray, 2022). Finally, reliability was evaluated using Cronbach's alpha, which measures the internal consistency of related question sets (Harkiolakis, 2021).

SPSS version 29 software was used for data analysis (IBM, 2024). Descriptive statistics were used to profile the demographic and occupational characteristics of the sample. Inferential statistics, specifically Spearman's rank-order for non-parametric distributions and Pearson's correlation analysis for normally distributed variables (Harkiolakis, 2021), were used to

investigate the relationship between eco-anxiety and employee engagement. Correlation analyses examined whether employee green behavior and company purpose moderated this relationship.

Throughout the research process, ethical considerations were rigorously upheld. Participation was voluntary, and informed consent was required for participation in the study. All data were anonymized and stored securely (Crow et al., 2007), with access restricted to me. This protocol safeguarded confidentiality and privacy, ensuring that participants' rights were protected at every stage of the study (Gray, 2022).

Research Questions

In alignment with the purpose of this study, the following central research question (CRQ) was adopted:

CRQ. What are the factors that serve as proxies for eco-anxiety and contribute to lowering employee engagement in private companies?

To support the CRQ the following research questions (RQs) are adopted:

Psychological Factors

RQ1. Does the lack of control over environmental issues associate with lower employee engagement in private companies?

RQ2. Does cognitive dissonance due to eco-anxiety associate with lower employee engagement in private companies?

RQ3. Does emotional exhaustion due to eco-anxiety associate with lower employee engagement in private companies?

RQ4. Does chronic stress related to climate change associate with lower employee engagement in private companies?

RQ5. Does low well-being due to eco-anxiety associate with lower employee engagement in private companies?

Organizational Factors

RQ6. Does the lack of corporate sustainability initiatives associate with lower employee engagement in private companies?

RQ7. Does a company's purpose statement without reference to sustainability associate with lower employee engagement in private companies?

RQ8. Does the absence of employee green behaviors associate with lower employee engagement in private companies?

RQ9. Does perceived lack of leadership support for environmental issues associate with lower employee engagement in private companies?

Socio-Environmental Factors

RQ10. Does media exposure to climate crises associate with lower employee engagement in private companies?

RQ11. Does uncertainty regarding environmental regulations associate with lower employee engagement in private companies?

RQ12. Do the perceived environmental regulatory and market pressures associate with lower employee engagement in private companies?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were considered to test the research questions (Figure 1):

H10. The lack of control over environmental issues does not associate with lower employee engagement in private companies.

H2₀. Cognitive dissonance due to eco-anxiety does not associate with lower employee engagement in private companies.

H3₀. Emotional exhaustion due to eco-anxiety does not associate with lower employee engagement in private companies.

H4₀. Chronic stress related to climate change does not associate with lower employee engagement in private companies.

H5₀. A low well-being due to eco-anxiety does not associate with lower employee engagement in private companies.

H6₀. The lack of corporate sustainability initiatives does not associate with lower employee engagement in private companies.

H7₀. A company purpose statement without reference to sustainability does not associate with lower employee engagement in private companies.

H8₀. The absence of employee green behaviors does not associate with lower employee engagement in private companies.

H9₀. Perceived lack of leadership support for environmental issues does not associate with lower employee engagement in private companies.

H10₀. Media exposure to climate crises does not associate with lower employee engagement in private companies.

H11₀. Uncertainty regarding environmental regulations does not associate with lower employee engagement in private companies.

H12₀. Perceived environmental regulatory and market pressures do not associate with lower employee engagement in private companies.

Significance of the Study

This study offers valuable insights for organizational leaders, human resources professionals, and policymakers aiming to support employees amid escalating environmental challenges. By identifying the psychological, organizational, and socio-environmental factors that serve as proxies for eco-anxiety and contribute to lowering employee engagement in private companies, this research provides practical insights into how climate-related stressors impact workplace dynamics. Specifically, it delivers actionable knowledge to the field of talent management by pinpointing the variables that most significantly influence employee engagement. This enables practitioners to design targeted interventions that promote psychological safety, meaningfulness, and availability at work (Kahn, 1990), even in the face of environmental concerns.

The findings may also inform the development of organizational strategies that reduce eco-anxiety, strengthen employee resilience, and align corporate sustainability efforts with employee expectations, contributing to goal 13 of the United Nations sustainable development goals (SDGs) (United Nations, n.d.). As eco-anxiety increasingly affects the workforce, particularly among younger generations, this research offers leaders of private organizations a timely framework to cultivate supportive, purpose-driven, and sustainable workplace cultures that enhance retention, productivity, and overall well-being.

From a theoretical perspective, this study advances the growing body of literature at the intersection of environmental psychology, organizational behavior, and occupational health by quantitatively examining eco-anxiety as a job demand within the job demands-resources (JD-R) framework (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007). It extends the transactional model of stress (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984) and Kahn's (1990) theory of employee engagement by exploring how eco-

anxiety, when compounded by insufficient psychological and organizational resources, undermines key conditions for engagement. By empirically testing the relationships between specific factors and employee engagement, this research offers a theoretical contribution, clarifying how climate-related stressors disrupt workplace functioning. Furthermore, the findings provide quantitative insights that can help refine concepts related to eco-anxiety and employee engagement and promote cross-disciplinary research.

Definitions of Key Terms

Chronic stress. The persistent mental health difficulties caused by prolonged exposure to climate-related stressors (Hickman et al., 2021).

Cognitive dissonance. The psychological discomfort that occurs when holding contradictory beliefs, ideas, or values, such as when environmental awareness conflicts with unsustainable behaviors (Festinger, 1957; Gifford, 2011).

Company purpose. The organization's ambition to effect positive change and provide employees with a profound sense of significance (Quinn & Thakor, 2018).

Eco-anxiety. The anxiety individuals experience due to concerns about environmental degradation and climate change (Pihkala, 2022b).

Employee green behaviors. The quantifiable employee behaviors that support environmental sustainability goals at work (Ones & Dilchert, 2012).

Employee engagement. The integration of individuals' selves into their work roles, encompassing physical, cognitive, and emotional aspects (Kahn, 1990).

Emotional exhaustion. The persistent state of physical and emotional exhaustion caused by high work and personal demands and a lack of sufficient emotional support in the workplace (Jin et al., 2020; Pihkala, 2020).

Lack of control. The feeling of personal powerlessness when confronting large-scale ecological crises (Hickman et al., 2021; Pihkala, 2020).

Lack of corporate sustainability initiatives. The absence of meaningful actions addressing social and environmental responsibility (Glavas & Kelley, 2014).

Media exposure. The stress caused by alarming media coverage of environmental issues (Niedzwiedz & Katikireddi, 2023).

Perceived environmental regulatory and market pressure. The institutional forces, such as regulations and market expectations, that influence stakeholders' engagement in sustainability efforts (Bansal & Roth, 2000).

Perceived lack of leadership support. The employee perception that leaders are not committed to or do not actively promote sustainability efforts (Robertson & Barling, 2017).

Uncertainty regarding environmental regulations. The unpredictable policies that reduce environmental concern (Lu, 2024).

Well-being. The positive condition that individuals and societies can experience (World Health Organization, 2022).

Summary

Eco-anxiety is emerging as a significant challenge in the workplace, as climate change creates not only environmental crises but also psychological strain on employees. Increasingly, employees expect companies to demonstrate genuine commitment to sustainability, and disengagement grows when organizations fail to align with these values. Traditional engagement strategies may no longer be sufficient, as climate-related distress threatens workforce motivation, satisfaction, and retention. Despite rising awareness of eco-anxiety, its impact on employee engagement remains underexplored.

The purpose of this study is to identify the psychological, organizational, and socio-environmental factors that serve as proxies for eco-anxiety and contribute to lowering employee engagement in private companies. Using a quantitative, non-experimental, correlational, cross-sectional design, data were collected through an online questionnaire targeting private-sector employees. Descriptive and inferential statistics are selected to explore associations between eco-anxiety and employee engagement while exploring how workplace factors, such as company purpose and employee green behaviors, may influence this dynamic.

Guided by Kahn's engagement theory, the transactional model of stress, and the job demands-resources model, this study investigates how eco-anxiety acts as a job demand that can undermine key psychological conditions for engagement if not balanced by adequate resources. Twelve factors across psychological, organizational, and socio-environmental dimensions are examined to provide a comprehensive understanding of this phenomenon.

By identifying the drivers of disengagement linked to eco-anxiety, this study offers valuable insights for organizations seeking to support employee well-being, strengthen resilience, and align sustainability efforts with workforce expectations. As climate-related distress continues to rise, the findings contribute practical knowledge to help companies build healthier, purpose-driven, and future-ready workplaces while advancing research at the intersection of mental health, sustainability, and organizational performance.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

Eco-anxiety is an emerging phenomenon (Pihkala, 2022b). This study aims to identify factors that act as proxies for eco-anxiety and contribute to lowering employee engagement in private companies, an area of growing interest with limited empirical research directly exploring this relationship (Ayassamy et al., 2024). To build a conceptual foundation for the study, a narrative literature review was conducted to integrate and synthesize existing knowledge, identify research gaps, and inform the development of the research framework, following the approach outlined by Torraco (2005). Narrative and systematic reviews serve distinct yet complementary roles in research synthesis (Greenhalgh et al., 2018). While systematic reviews rely on predefined inclusion criteria and often incorporate statistical meta-analysis, narrative reviews provide a more flexible approach, allowing for the exploration of diverse themes and conceptual linkages across disciplines (Sukhera, 2022). By offering interpretation, critique, and deeper insight into complex topics (Greenhalgh et al., 2018; Sukhera, 2022), the narrative review method aligns well with the objectives of this research and supports a more comprehensive understanding of the theoretical framework (Figure 1).

This review examines how eco-anxiety may serve as a stressor that affects employee engagement, drawing from relevant psychological, organizational, and socio-environmental factors. To establish a theoretical foundation, this chapter discusses key theories that inform the study, including Kahn's (1990) engagement theory, the transactional model of stress (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984), and the job demands-resources (JD-R) model (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007). This chapter is structured into three sections: the conceptual foundations of eco-anxiety and employee engagement, the theoretical framework guiding the study, and the key factors contributing to eco-anxiety and lower employee engagement.

To ensure a comprehensive and methodologically sound review, an initial search strategy was implemented across major academic databases, including EBSCOhost, Google Scholar, JSTOR, ProQuest, PsycINFO, SAGE Journals, and Scopus. The literature search was conducted in March 2025 using the following keywords individually and as a combination: "eco-anxiety", "climate anxiety", and "employee engagement". Boolean operators AND and OR were used with the search terms to improve recall and precision. The search was restricted to articles published between 2015 and 2025 to prioritize current discussions and emerging research trends. The selection process applied the inherent filters within each database to ensure the retrieval of peer-reviewed journal articles. Opinion pieces, and non-English publications were excluded to maintain academic rigor.

Given the interdisciplinary nature of this research, additional sources on employee engagement, stress, psychological responses to climate change, and workplace sustainability behaviors were included to provide theoretical depth. These sources help bridge conceptual gaps and highlight the lack of studies directly examining the relationship between eco-anxiety and employee engagement, emphasizing the need for further research to support employees facing environmental concerns. The following sections present a thematic synthesis of the selected studies, organized to align with the research focus.

Eco-Anxiety

Eco-anxiety has emerged as a significant psychological response to the escalating climate crisis and environmental degradation, gaining recognition in both public discourse and academic literature (Pihkala, 2020). Initially conceptualized as the "chronic fear of environmental doom" (Clayton et al., 2017, p. 68), eco-anxiety is now understood as a multidimensional phenomenon encompassing emotional, cognitive, behavioral, and social dimensions (Hogg et al., 2021, 2024).

It manifests through persistent worry, rumination, guilt, grief, helplessness, and anger, often accompanied by functional impairments such as difficulty concentrating, sleep disturbances, and reduced work performance (Clayton & Karazsia, 2020). Unlike general anxiety disorders, eco-anxiety is considered a rational and even adaptive response to real and immediate environmental threats (Pihkala, 2020; Whitmarsh et al., 2022).

Despite growing recognition of eco-anxiety as a legitimate psychological phenomenon, its conceptual boundaries remain debated (Coffey et al., 2021; Lykins et al., 2023). Scholars note its overlap with related constructs such as ecological grief or eco-guilt (Cunsolo & Ellis, 2018), eco-anger (Stanley et al., 2021), and solastalgia (Albrecht et al., 2007; Lykins et al., 2023), which refers to the emotional distress experienced due to environmental changes that directly affect one's native land. This conceptual fluidity poses methodological challenges for measurement, as Martin et al. (2023) highlight the current lack of validated tools for assessing eco-anxiety across diverse populations. While scales like the climate anxiety scale (CAS) (Clayton & Karazsia, 2020) and the Hogg eco-anxiety scale (HEAS) (Hogg et al., 2021) provide useful frameworks, concerns persist about their cross-cultural applicability (Hogg et al., 2023) and their emphasis on impairment and excessive worry, which may overlook adaptive coping mechanisms and cognitive appraisals of climate anxiety (Crandon et al., 2024). Recent validation studies found strong support for the HEAS model but mixed results for the CAS (Hogg et al., 2023), underscoring the need for further investigation into the psychometric performance of these tools across different populations.

Additionally, most empirical studies focus on individual-level experiences of eco-anxiety, often neglecting its presence in organizational contexts where collective eco-emotions influence workplace dynamics (de Lange et al., 2022). This gap is particularly relevant given the

increasing recognition of eco-anxiety as not merely a personal concern but a broader social and professional issue affecting employee well-being, organizational climate, and employee engagement (Ayassamy et al., 2024; Brooks & Greenberg, 2022; de Lange et al., 2022). While eco-anxiety is widely acknowledged as a valid emotional response to ecological threats, further theoretical refinement, operationalization, and empirical validation are needed, particularly within workplace settings.

Impacts of Eco-Anxiety

Eco-anxiety affects more than just individual mental health; it also influences workplace behaviors, social interactions, and life choices (Boluda-Verdú et al., 2022; Hickman et al., 2021; Vercammen et al., 2023). Research consistently links eco-anxiety to emotional distress, including anxiety, anger, depression, despair, sleep disruption, and an overall decline in well-being (Boluda-Verdú et al., 2022; Hickman et al., 2021; Hogg et al., 2024; Niedzwiedz & Katikireddi, 2023; Pihkala, 2020).

In the workplace, studies show that eco-anxiety contributes to reduced productivity, difficulty concentrating, and withdrawal from work (Andretta, 2023; Ayassamy et al., 2024; Boluda-Verdú et al., 2022; Brooks & Greenberg, 2022). Employees experiencing eco-anxiety often feel powerless, frustrated by leadership's inaction, and disillusioned with corporate sustainability efforts (2023 Net Positive Employee Barometer, 2023; Humacap, 2025). A systematic review found that 30 out of 33 correlational studies reported a significant positive association between eco-anxiety and mental health (Cosh et al., 2024). However, one study suggests that climate-related anxiety itself may not directly affect mental health. Instead, factors such as socioeconomic status, education, and age play a more significant role (Drion et al., 2024).

The relationship between eco-anxiety and behavior is complex and sometimes contradictory. While some research suggests eco-anxiety can drive pro-environmental behavior (Pavani et al., 2023), other studies highlight its potential to induce eco-paralysis, where individuals become immobilized by overwhelming feelings of helplessness and despair (Innocenti et al., 2023). Additionally, climate indifference, as a component of denial, represents another possible emotional reaction (Wullenkord et al., 2021). Peer pressure can also lead to the suppression or denial of eco-anxiety (Brulle & Norgaard, 2019). These divergent responses suggest that eco-anxiety exists on a spectrum, with factors such as coping mechanisms, organizational culture, and perceived agency influencing whether it serves as a motivator or a barrier to action.

Workplace studies further refine this understanding. For example, Joshua et al. (2022) found that eco-anxiety moderates the relationship between restaurant green attributes and voluntary green behaviors: high eco-anxiety weakens the positive impact of perceived environmental orientation on discretionary pro-environmental actions while having no significant effect on required green behaviors. This suggests that while strong green organizational cultures encourage voluntary pro-environmental behaviors, eco-anxiety may inhibit employee engagement, particularly in workplaces where environmental commitments appear weak or inconsistent.

Eco-anxiety also shapes major life decisions, particularly among younger generations, influencing choices related to parenthood, career paths, and geographic mobility (van den Broek, 2023; Vercammen et al., 2023). These existential concerns underscore the broader sociocultural significance of eco-anxiety, positioning it as not only a mental health issue but also a factor reshaping demographic trends, labor markets, and societal resilience. Given its far-reaching

effects, managing eco-anxiety through supportive coping strategies, proactive employee engagement, and collective action is crucial, with organizations playing a key role in fostering competence and well-being in climate-related efforts (de Lange et al., 2022).

Despite the expanding body of literature, gaps remain. Most research focuses on individual coping strategies and psychological outcomes, with limited exploration of organizational interventions that could mitigate eco-anxiety (Ayassamy et al., 2024; Brooks & Greenberg, 2022). Moreover, studies are predominantly conducted in Western contexts, raising concerns about the generalizability of findings across diverse cultural and socioeconomic environments (Coffey et al., 2021; Jarrett et al., 2024; Ogunbode et al., 2022). Addressing these gaps requires more nuanced, context-sensitive research examining eco-anxiety within complex systems, including workplaces, communities, and international organizations.

Demographic and Psychological Profiles of Eco-Anxiety

Eco-anxiety manifests differently across individuals, with personality traits, cognitive styles, and social support influencing whether it leads to constructive action or psychological distress (Kankawale & Niedzwiedz, 2023). Helm et al. (2018) identified two primary coping strategies: an adaptive approach and maladaptive avoidance. While some individuals channel eco-anxiety into proactive environmental behaviors, others experience eco-paralysis or disengagement (Innocenti et al., 2023). Personality traits also play a role: conscientiousness, for example, correlates positively with habitual ecological worry and eco-guilt, suggesting that highly conscientious individuals may experience heightened eco-anxiety alongside a stronger sense of environmental responsibility (Rai, 2024). Cognitive styles such as rumination and low self-efficacy exacerbate negative impacts, whereas social support, collective action, and hope mediate distress and promote resilience (Bishop & Willis, 2014).

Demographic patterns indicate that eco-anxiety is more prevalent among women, younger adults, and individuals with higher education levels (Clayton & Karazsia, 2020; Coffey et al., 2021; Hickman et al., 2021; Niedzwiedz & Katikireddi, 2023). A study across 25 European countries found that women reported higher levels of concern than men, and individuals aged 60–69 were more concerned than those aged 15–19. Additionally, higher levels of education were stronger predictors of concern than income (Niedzwiedz & Katikireddi, 2023). Moreover, individuals from marginalized and vulnerable communities, who face greater direct impacts of climate change, report higher levels of climate anxiety (Coffey et al., 2021; Hayes et al., 2018). There is also a lack of studies evaluating the impact of eco-anxiety in the Global South (Coffey et al., 2021).

Addressing eco-anxiety is essential for public health, highlighting the need for interventions and further research to reduce its impact (Jarrett et al., 2024; Kankawale & Niedzwiedz, 2023). Although eco-anxiety is increasingly recognized as influencing employee engagement and retention (Andretta, 2023; Ayassamy et al., 2024; Brooks & Greenberg, 2022), research on workplace-specific psychological profiles remains limited. Addressing these gaps is essential for developing targeted interventions and inclusive organizational policies that support diverse employee populations in navigating ecological distress.

Employee Engagement

Employee engagement is a widely studied but inconsistently defined construct in organizational behavior (Iddagoda et al., 2016; Saks & Gruman, 2014; Shuck & Wollard, 2010). This complex concept includes work engagement, job engagement, and overall engagement (Lee et al., 2017; Saks & Gruman, 2014). It reflects employees' emotional, cognitive, and physical investment in their work roles (Kahn, 1990) and is often characterized by vigor, dedication, and

absorption (Schaufeli et al., 2002). Engaged employees exhibit high energy, strong involvement, and a positive connection with their work (Macey & Schneider, 2008).

Although employee engagement is associated with concepts such as motivation (Salanova et al., 2005), job satisfaction (Harter et al., 2002), and organizational commitment (González-Romá et al., 2006), it remains theoretically fragmented. Some scholars view it as a multidimensional construct involving cognitive, emotional, and behavioral components, while others argue for a unitary perspective (Hakeem & Gulzar, 2014; Sun & Bunchapattanasakda, 2019).

Despite its recognized benefits, including improved job performance, lower turnover, and increased organizational commitment (Bakker, 2011; Harter et al., 2002), employee engagement research faces challenges. The lack of a universal definition, inconsistent measurement approaches, and reliance on cross-sectional self-report data limit generalizability and causal inferences (Bailey et al., 2017). Additionally, while existing studies focus on workplace factors, external stressors such as climate anxiety remain underexplored (Ayassamy et al., 2024). Addressing these gaps is important for developing a more comprehensive understanding of employee engagement, particularly in response to contemporary challenges affecting workforce well-being.

Drivers and Outcomes of Employee Engagement

Employee engagement is shaped by a combination of organizational, job-related, and individual factors, making it a continuous and evolving process rather than a singular event (Michel et al., 2021; Sonnentag et al., 2021). Key organizational elements, such as culture, leadership, and high-performance work practices, significantly influence work engagement and employee well-being (Kataria, 2014; Ogruk & Anderson, 2018). Leadership plays a key role in

creating a healthy work environment by setting policies, priorities, and practices that support employee well-being and workplace health (Benesty et al., 2024; Kaluza et al., 2019). These factors directly impact employees' overall well-being, suggesting that leaders' perceptions and actions have cascading effects on employee engagement and exhaustion. However, the research lacks generalizability due to a non-representative sample, and the two quantitative studies yielded differing results. Despite these challenges, aligning company culture with environmental and social responsibility can enhance employee engagement (Kaluza et al., 2019).

The strong influence of leadership on employee engagement emphasizes how leaders create psychological conditions that either facilitate or hinder engagement (Hauff et al., 2022; Kaluza et al., 2019). When employees feel psychologically invested in their roles, they exhibit positive citizenship behaviors, contributing to organizational effectiveness (Kataria, 2014). Psychological capital also plays a key role, as employees with high levels of optimism, resilience, and self-efficacy are more likely to engage fully and authentically in their work (De Waal & Pienaar, 2013; Kataria, 2014). Similarly, employees whose values align with their company's mission tend to demonstrate higher work engagement levels (Ogruk & Anderson, 2018). While psychological capital generally correlates positively with work engagement, some studies indicate inconsistencies in its direct impact (De Waal & Pienaar, 2013).

Leadership and communication are central to fostering psychological safety and trust, which are essential for engagement (Bailey et al., 2017). According to Bailey et al. (2017), employee engagement is influenced by five key factors: psychological states, job design, leadership, organizational and team dynamics, and strategic interventions. Job resources, such as supervisor support, recognition, and task variety, enhance engagement, while excessive job demands can lead to disengagement (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007; Lesener et al., 2020).

An emerging driver of engagement is environmental consciousness, particularly among younger employees (Niedzwiedz & Katikireddi, 2023). Green human resource management (GHRM) practices, such as sustainability initiatives, pro-environmental training, and corporate climate commitments, positively impact employee engagement (Ababneh et al., 2021; Baykal & Bayraktar, 2022; Dumont et al., 2016). Employee work engagement also has a spillover effect, spreading throughout the workplace (Bakker, 2011). The connection between GHRM and engagement is influenced by mediating factors like psychological ownership and moderated by transformational leadership (Ababneh et al., 2021; Baykal & Bayraktar, 2022). Organizations integrating environmental and social responsibility into engagement strategies may see increased motivation and commitment among employees.

Higher employee engagement is linked to numerous positive individual and organizational outcomes. Engaged employees exhibit higher job performance, lower turnover intentions, and greater organizational commitment (Gupta & Sharma, 2016; Halbesleben et al., 2009; Saks & Gruman, 2014). Research connects engagement to improved morale, enhanced task performance, and discretionary efforts contributing to organizational success, with task performance being the most strongly supported outcome (Bailey et al., 2017). Gallup's 2020 meta-analysis of 456 studies across 276 organizations in 96 countries, involving 112,312 work units and 2.7 million employees, reaffirmed the strong correlation between employee engagement and key performance outcomes, including customer loyalty, profitability, productivity, safety, absenteeism, well-being, and organizational citizenship (Gallup, 2023). Employees with higher self-efficacy, psychological safety, and work meaningfulness are also more likely to drive innovation and organizational change (Albrecht et al., 2023).

Conversely, disengagement correlates with absenteeism, reduced productivity, and "quiet quitting," where employees meet only minimal job expectations (Burton et al., 2017; Merrill et al., 2013; Pevec, 2023). A meta-analysis by Harter et al. (2002) found that engagement is significantly linked to key business outcomes such as profitability, customer loyalty, and employee retention. Additionally, Gallup (2024a) estimates that low engagement costs the global economy \$8.8 trillion, accounting for 9% of global GDP, while employee engagement in the U.S. reached its lowest level in a decade in 2024 (Harter, 2025). These findings highlight the economic imperative of fostering an engaged workforce (Govender et al., 2022).

However, excessive engagement can have unintended consequences. Overly engaged employees, particularly in high-demand roles or unsupportive environments, may experience burnout (Halbesleben et al., 2009). Balancing engagement with well-being is particularly relevant in the context of climate-related stressors. Emerging research suggests that unaddressed eco-anxiety can contribute to disengagement and quiet quitting, especially when employees perceive a disconnect between their environmental values and their organization's priorities (Andretta, 2023; 2023 Net Positive Employee Barometer, 2023). Employee engagement is a dynamic and multifaceted process influenced by organizational, individual, and job-related factors, and fostering it effectively requires balancing engagement with well-being while adapting to emerging challenges such as environmental concerns and evolving workplace dynamics.

Limitations of Employee Engagement Literature

The findings of employee engagement studies have informed workplace practices, but some organizational stakeholders continue to struggle with modern challenges, highlighting the need for employee engagement research itself to address. A key limitation of employee

engagement research is its heavy reliance on cross-sectional, self-reported data, which introduces self-report biases and limits causal inference (Bailey et al., 2017). Additionally, a lack of cultural and demographic diversity in studies further constrains the generalizability of findings (Bailey et al., 2017). Most employee engagement research is conducted in Western contexts and applied broadly across industries and regions without accounting for cultural variations in employee engagement dynamics (Coffey et al., 2021). This gap underscores the need for cross-cultural studies that examine how employee engagement functions in diverse socio-economic and ecological settings.

Modern workplace challenges, including climate-related stressors, remote work dynamics, and shifting employee values, call for a broader conceptualization of employee engagement (Surma et al., 2021). Ayassamy et al. (2024) suggest that factors such as eco-anxiety, job sustainability perceptions, and corporate environmental responsibility significantly influence employee engagement, yet they remain underexplored. While the literature primarily emphasizes internal organizational factors like leadership, incentives, and recognition as key drivers of employee engagement (Bailey et al., 2017; Kavya & Padmavathy, 2017), it largely overlooks external influences.

Moreover, research has disproportionately focused on work engagement-enhancing factors while neglecting job demands, such as emotional strain, as critical contributors to disengagement (Ahmed, 2019). This oversight limits understanding of how work-related pressures deplete employees' psychological resources, ultimately reducing employee engagement. Studies also tend to prioritize organizational outcomes, such as performance, retention, and productivity, while underestimating the role of employee well-being (Robertson & Cooper, 2010). Robertson and Cooper (2010) advocate for a comprehensive employee

engagement approach that incorporates psychological well-being, ensuring a balance between organizational and employee needs. To stay relevant, employee engagement research must include well-being, resilience, and environmental consciousness. Future studies should draw from organizational behavior, environmental psychology, and mental health to create adaptive, holistic frameworks for today's workforce.

Theoretical Perspectives

To examine theoretical frameworks that explain how eco-anxiety may shape or influence employee engagement, the following sections introduce three key theories: Kahn's (1990) engagement theory, the transactional model of stress (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984), and the job demands-resources model (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007). These theories offer complementary insights into the psychological and organizational factors shaping engagement.

Engagement Theory

Kahn's (1990) engagement theory remains foundational in employee engagement research (Rothmann, 2014; Saks & Gruman, 2014; Sambrook, 2021). Drawing on motivation theories (Alderfer, 1969; Herzberg et al., 1959; Maslow, 1943), Kahn (1990) defined engagement as the physical, cognitive, and emotional investment individuals make in their work roles. He identified three key conditions for engagement: meaningfulness, psychological safety, and psychological availability. His model emerged as organizational research shifted from mechanistic views to recognizing emotional and cognitive influences on performance (Ashforth & Humphrey, 1995).

Kahn (1990) and Berg et al. (2010) argued that employees engage more when their work aligns with personal values (meaningfulness), fostering commitment. Moreover, psychological safety, or the freedom to express opinions without fear, is nurtured through trust and fairness

(Bailey et al., 2017). Finally, psychological availability refers to having the mental, physical, and emotional capacity to be present at work (Byrne et al., 2017). Engagement, therefore, is dynamic, shaped by personal traits, job characteristics, and organizational culture (Kahn, 1990).

Researchers continue to apply Kahn's theory to workplace behaviors, reinforcing its contemporary relevance (Bailey et al., 2017; Bakker, 2011; Huang, 2021; Soane et al., 2012).

However, some critique inconsistencies in engagement measurement, questioning predictive validity and global applicability (Anthony-McMann et al., 2016; Rothmann, 2014).

Eco-anxiety presents an emerging workplace challenge that can undermine Kahn's three psychological conditions: meaningfulness, safety, and availability (Ayassamy et al., 2024).

Employees struggling with climate-related distress may find work meaningless if their organization lacks environmental commitment (Ayassamy et al., 2024). Psychological safety may diminish when employees fear career repercussions for voicing sustainability concerns (Pacheco et al., 2015). Chronic stress over environmental issues can deplete cognitive and emotional resources, reducing psychological availability (Pihkala, 2020). Kahn's framework (1990) underscores the need for organizations to address eco-anxiety, enabling employees to navigate environmental concerns while maintaining engagement.

Transactional Model of Stress

The transactional model of stress, developed by Lazarus and Folkman (1984), marked a shift in stress research by emphasizing cognitive processes in stress responses. Earlier models, such as Selye's (1956), focused primarily on physiological reactions. In contrast, Lazarus and Folkman (1984) conceptualized stress as a dynamic interaction between individuals and their environment, where cognitive appraisals and coping strategies determine whether a stressor leads to distress or adaptation. The process begins with primary appraisal, in which individuals

evaluate an encounter to determine if it poses a threat (Lazarus, 1990; Lazarus & Folkman, 1984; MacNair & Elliott, 1992). If deemed stressful, secondary appraisal follows, where individuals assess their resources to cope (Groomes & Leahy, 2002; Lazarus, 1990; Lazarus & Folkman, 1984; MacNair & Elliott, 1992). Coping strategies may be personal (e.g., resilience, optimism) or external (e.g., organizational support, social networks). MacNair and Elliott (1992) also identify distinct coping patterns. The effectiveness of these strategies directly influences emotional and physiological well-being (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984).

Since its introduction, the transactional model of stress has been applied across various domains (Berjot & Gillet, 2011; Goh et al., 2010; Margaret et al., 2018; Obbarius et al., 2021; Spătaru et al., 2024). Its strength lies in offering a nuanced understanding of how individuals perceive and respond to stress. However, empirical validation remains problematic due to partial measurement and limited sample sizes (Berjot & Gillet, 2011; Obbarius et al., 2021; Spătaru et al., 2024).

One emerging application of this model is in understanding eco-anxiety, which acts as a chronic stressor, repeatedly triggering strain and emotional exhaustion (Ayassamy et al., 2024; Brown et al., 2014; Ojala, 2016; Pihkala, 2022a). Employees frequently encounter alarming climate news or direct ecological losses, leading to threat appraisals (Clayton & Karazsia, 2020). Coping depends on available support and resources that can mitigate climate-induced mental ill-health at work, while a lack of support may lead to job tension, workplace hostility, decision-making difficulties, or even turnover intentions (Brooks & Greenberg, 2022).

Ojala (2016) adapted the concept of coping to ecological contexts by categorizing coping strategies into three distinct types: *problem-focused coping*, which involves taking practical actions to address environmental issues (e.g., reducing personal carbon emissions by cycling

instead of driving); *emotion-focused coping*, which includes managing emotional responses to environmental threats (e.g., discussing climate-related anxieties with peers or engaging in stress-reducing practices); and *meaning-focused coping*, which entails finding positive meaning or purpose in environmental engagement (e.g., interpreting climate activism as a contribution to intergenerational justice and a sustainable future). The transactional model of stress underscores the critical role of organizational contexts in shaping eco-anxiety responses, ultimately influencing employee engagement and well-being.

Job Demands-Resources

The job demands-resources (JD-R) model, developed by Bakker and Demerouti (2007), extends earlier occupational stress frameworks, particularly Karasek's (1979) demand-control model and Siegrist's (1996) effort-reward imbalance model. Rather than focusing on a limited set of job characteristics, the JD-R model categorizes all characteristics into either job demands (factors requiring sustained effort) or job resources (structures that foster motivation and coping). Excessive or chronic demands can deplete mental and physical reserves, leading to burnout, stress-related disorders, and diminished performance (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007, 2017; Lesener et al., 2020). In contrast, abundant job resources, such as supportive leadership, cohesive teams, and clear opportunities for advancement, stimulate motivation and engagement, often buffering stressors (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007, 2017).

By 2017, Bakker and Demerouti reframed the model as the job demands-resources theory, addressing the limitations of the previous version and highlighting how resources can spark a "gain spiral" of growing resilience and engagement, whereas unmitigated demands may trigger a "loss spiral" of rising stress and declining performance (Bakker & Demerouti, 2017).

Empirical research in diverse occupational settings confirmed the model's robustness (Bakker, 2011; Bakker & Demerouti, 2017).

Interventions often aim to increase job resources (e.g., social support, career development) while managing or modifying demands (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007, 2017). Research also shows that personal resources, such as self-efficacy and optimism, mediate these processes (Xanthopoulou et al., 2009).

Eco-anxiety resembles a job demand when employees grapple with news of environmental crises (Clayton et al., 2017). This strain can result in disengagement or burnout if insufficient resources exist (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007, 2017). However, in organizations committed to sustainability or practicing GHRM (Dumont et al., 2016), eco-anxiety may function as a motivating demand that drives pro-environmental behaviors (Innocenti et al., 2023).

Integrated Framework

Building on Miles et al. (2014) and insights from three foundational theories: Kahn's (1990) engagement theory, Lazarus and Folkman's (1984) transactional model of stress, and Bakker and Demerouti's (2007) JD-R model, this study proposes an integrated theoretical framework to explain how eco-anxiety functions as a stressor that undermines the psychological conditions necessary for employee engagement. As illustrated in Figure 1, eco-anxiety emerges as a job demand, perpetuated by threat appraisals, which ultimately impede the core elements of engagement: meaningfulness, safety, and availability.

First, Kahn's (1990) engagement theory highlights the emotional and cognitive underpinnings of work engagement, illustrating how eco-anxiety can erode psychological safety and diminish employees' sense of meaning in their roles. Second, the transactional model of

stress (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984) explains how eco-anxiety triggers both primary and secondary appraisals, influencing the coping strategies employees choose. When employees adopt problem-focused coping, they may advocate for CSR initiatives; however, emotion-focused coping often leads to withdrawal behaviors that ultimately reduce engagement. Finally, the JD-R model (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007) provides a structural perspective by framing eco-anxiety as a “demand” that depletes energy and well-being if organizations fail to offer sufficient resources.

Eco-anxiety is a multifaceted experience influenced by personal, organizational, and socio-environmental factors (Ayassamy et al., 2024; Pihkala, 2022a). These elements, alone or combined, can erode employee engagement, which hinges on meaningfulness, psychological safety, and both physical and emotional availability (Kahn, 1990). Within this integrated framework, the psychological factors (lack of control, cognitive dissonance, emotional exhaustion, chronic stress, low well-being), organizational factors (lack of corporate sustainability initiatives, weak company purpose, limited employee green behaviors, perceived lack of leadership support), and socio-environmental factors (media exposure, uncertainty regarding regulations, perceived external pressures) can be conceptualized as interacting influences on eco-anxiety and, consequently, on employee engagement.

These factors not only shape employees’ internal appraisals but also intersect with organizational resources, collectively determining engagement outcomes and offering potential avenues for interventions. By uniting these three theoretical perspectives, the study addresses individual, job-related, and broader organizational processes that can exacerbate or mitigate eco-anxiety, thereby affecting employee engagement. Such a comprehensive approach is critical in today’s complex work environments, where external environmental pressures increasingly pervade organizational life and employees seek meaningful, sustainable work experiences.

Psychological Factors

Eco-anxiety is deeply rooted in psychological experiences that shape how individuals perceive and respond to environmental threats (Clayton & Karazsia, 2020; Hickman et al., 2021; Pihkala, 2020). This section explores key psychological contributors to eco-anxiety and their implications for employee well-being and engagement.

Lack of Control. Employees often feel powerless in the face of large-scale environmental challenges, leading to anxiety and hopelessness that undermine their psychological availability (Hickman et al., 2021; Kahn, 1990; Pihkala, 2020). Over time, this sense of helplessness can reinforce negative beliefs, such as low self-efficacy, further diminishing their commitment to work (Bishop & Willis, 2014; De Waal & Pienaar, 2013). However, recognizing that individuals can influence factors contributing to the global climate crisis fosters an “internal locus of control”, a personal sense of responsibility and action. This mindset empowers employees to address environmental issues by changing their behavior (Ikiugu et al., 2015).

Cognitive Dissonance. Cognitive dissonance occurs when holding contradictory beliefs, ideas, or values, such as when environmental awareness conflicts with unsustainable behaviors (Festinger, 1957; Gifford, 2011). If unresolved, the dissonance can cause eco-paralysis (Innocenti et al., 2023), where employees feel trapped between personal ethics and organizational demands, weakening emotional investment (Kahn, 1990). Conversely, if the organization acknowledges these tensions and supports employee-driven sustainability initiatives, dissonance decreases, preserving engagement (Gomes et al., 2023; Mendes et al., 2021).

Emotional Exhaustion. Persistent physical and emotional exhaustion can result from high work and personal demands, combined with insufficient emotional support in the workplace (Jin et al., 2020; Pihkala, 2020). Repeated exposure to climate-related stressors may further contribute to emotional exhaustion (Andretta, 2023; Pihkala, 2020), leading to reduced focus and creativity at work (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007). This exhaustion also correlates with burnout, absenteeism, and turnover (Halbesleben & Bowler, 2007; Vandenberg et al., 2017). Organizational resources can mitigate fatigue and sustain engagement (de Lange et al., 2022).

Chronic Stress. Chronic stress stems from sustained worry over environmental harm, extreme weather, and future uncertainties (Hickman et al., 2021). Over time, it affects physical and mental health, resulting in disturbed sleep, reduced cognitive functioning, and disengagement (Clayton & Karazsia, 2020). Without coping mechanisms, stress can escalate and reinforce feelings of helplessness (Boluda-Verdú et al., 2022; Lazarus & Folkman, 1984).

Low Well-Being. Well-being is a positive condition that individuals and societies can experience (World Health Organization, 2022). Eco-anxiety is linked to negative mental health outcomes, often leading to functional impairment and lower self-rated well-being (Boluda-Verdú et al., 2022; Niedzwiedz & Katikireddi, 2023). However, it can also foster a pro-ecological mindset and encourage environmental engagement, highlighting its dual role in mental health and behavior (Boluda-Verdú et al., 2022; Niedzwiedz & Katikireddi, 2023). In the workplace, eco-anxiety can both hinder and motivate engagement. While its psychological toll may reduce well-being and productivity, structured interventions mitigate negative effects and harness eco-anxiety as a driver of pro-environmental behaviors (Ayassamy et al., 2024).

Organizational Factors

Organizational context significantly shapes how employees experience and cope with eco-anxiety (Dumont et al., 2016; Pavani et al., 2023; Su & Swanson, 2019). The following section examines factors impacting employee responses to climate-related stress.

Lack of Corporate Sustainability Initiatives. Meaningful social and environmental responsibility initiatives in the workplace can influence employees' perception of their organization's environmental commitment, potentially reducing eco-anxiety and encouraging green behaviors, though required behaviors are less affected by eco-anxiety (Glavas & Kelley, 2014; Joshua et al., 2022). Those initiatives positively impact employee well-being, with organizational trust and identification mediating this relationship, fostering engagement in a supportive corporate environment (Su & Swanson, 2019). The absence of sustainability programs (e.g., waste reduction, energy conservation) may signal neglect, increasing stress and disengagement (de Lange et al., 2022). Conversely, research suggests that visible sustainability efforts help shape a positive psychological green climate, alleviating eco-anxiety and reinforcing employee engagement (Dumont et al., 2016).

Company Purpose. Company purpose reflects the overarching mission, values, and societal impact of an organization (Quinn & Thakor, 2018). Employees value alignment between their personal values and corporate social responsibility, which enhances commitment and job satisfaction (Glavas & Kelley, 2014). A strong, environmentally oriented purpose fosters meaningfulness (Kahn, 1990), while neglecting or trivializing climate responsibilities can create ethical dissonance and erode engagement (Festinger, 1957). Authentic and clear "green" messaging fosters collective action, reinforcing employee commitment (Baykal & Bayraktar, 2022).

Employee Green Behaviors. Individual actions that support environmental sustainability goals at work, such as recycling or reducing energy consumption, are shaped by organizational support (Ones & Dilchert, 2012). Eco-anxiety may drive pro-environmental efforts, but “eco-paralysis” can occur if workplace norms or resources are inadequate (Innocenti et al., 2023; Joshua et al., 2022). Providing sustainability training, setting green performance goals, and recognizing eco-friendly initiatives can enhance employee self-efficacy, support constructive responses to eco-anxiety, and boost engagement (Dumont et al., 2016; Pavani et al., 2023).

Perceived Lack of Leadership Support. Leadership signals organizational priorities and allocates resources (Hauff et al., 2022). Ignoring climate concerns can worsen eco-anxiety by limiting psychological safety, leading to individuals struggling to develop adaptive coping mechanisms and maladaptive anxiety responses (Clayton, 2020; Kahn, 1990). In contrast, leaders who advocate for green policies and set tangible environmental targets reinforce employees’ environmental values, thus promoting employee engagement (Robertson & Barling, 2017).

Socio-Environmental Factors

External environmental forces can heighten eco-anxiety or motivate proactive responses depending on organizational and individual capacities (Ayassamy et al., 2024; Brulle & Norgaard, 2019; Niedzwiedz & Katikireddi, 2023). This section highlights how broader systemic factors intersect with workplace experiences of eco-anxiety.

Media Exposure to Climate Crises. Frequent and intense media coverage of ecological disasters amplifies feelings of urgency and vulnerability, fueling eco-anxiety (Coe et al., 2023; Loll et al., 2023; Niedzwiedz & Katikireddi, 2023; Ogunbode et al., 2022). Prolonged exposure to climate-related stressors can further lead to cognitive-emotional impairment, especially when organizational responses are perceived as inadequate (Boluda-Verdú et al., 2022). However, by

integrating climate change into broader social narratives and connecting media reports to tangible sustainability initiatives, organizations can help counter social inertia and foster proactive engagement (Brulle & Norgaard, 2019).

Uncertainty Regarding Environmental Regulations. Environmental regulations and industry contexts shape perceptions of uncertainty about environmental policies among organizations and employees (Lu, 2024). The regulatory ambiguity can provoke job-related anxiety, undermining employees' psychological availability (Kahn, 1990). Transparent communication and proactive adaptation strategies can help mitigate these anxieties, fostering psychological security and sustaining employee engagement (Brooks & Greenberg, 2022).

Perceived Environmental Regulatory and Market Pressures. Institutional forces, such as regulations and market expectations, shape stakeholder engagement in sustainability (Bansal & Roth, 2000). Employees perceive pro-environmental pressure differently: some see it as a challenge that drives engagement, while others view it as a threat, leading to disengagement (Yang et al., 2025). Pressure from employees and local communities boosts corporate sustainability, whereas distant regulatory demands can reduce motivation (Ernst et al., 2022). Nonetheless, with clear strategies and sufficient resources, organizations can turn eco-anxiety and external pressures into opportunities for sustainability initiatives, enhancing employee engagement (Ayassamy et al., 2024).

Summary

This study investigates how eco-anxiety may act as a contributing factor to lowering employee engagement in private companies. The literature review was guided by a narrative approach, selected for its flexibility in exploring emerging concepts across interdisciplinary fields. A comprehensive search strategy was used to identify relevant peer-reviewed studies,

drawing from various databases. Keywords included “eco-anxiety,” “climate anxiety,” and “employee engagement,” with non-English publications and grey literature excluded to maintain academic rigor. In total, 108 peer-reviewed articles and scholarly sources were reviewed and synthesized to provide an integrated understanding of how eco-anxiety influences employee engagement within organizational contexts.

The review explored both practical and theoretical dimensions. Practically, it examined the concepts of eco-anxiety and employee engagement, then it identified key psychological factors such as emotional exhaustion, cognitive dissonance, and chronic stress, along with organizational conditions like weak sustainability initiatives, lack of leadership support, and value misalignment. Broader socio-environmental influences, like media exposure, regulatory uncertainty, and market pressures, were also found to intensify eco-anxiety in the workplace, potentially leading to disengagement.

Theoretically, three models were reviewed to understand the relationship between eco-anxiety and employee engagement: the engagement theory, the transactional model of stress, and the job demands-resources model. Together, these frameworks support an integrated perspective where eco-anxiety is viewed as a job demand that disrupts core psychological conditions for engagement, meaningfulness, psychological safety, and emotional availability, especially in unsupportive organizational environments.

Across the literature, there is growing agreement on the significance of eco-anxiety and the importance of engagement to organizational outcomes. However, existing research remains fragmented, often focused on individual-level experiences, predominantly in Western contexts. These limitations highlight a clear gap and the need for empirical research that examines measurable indicators of eco-anxiety and their relationship with employee engagement.

Addressing this gap will help inform future theory and guide organizational strategies that promote employee well-being in the face of environmental challenges.

Chapter 3: Research Method

This study addressed the issue of low employee engagement in private companies, which may be influenced by rising levels of eco-anxiety among the workforce. The purpose of this quantitative, non-experimental, correlational, cross-sectional study was to identify factors that act as proxies for eco-anxiety and explore their relationship with employee engagement.

This chapter presents a comprehensive overview of the research methodology and design used in the study. It begins by outlining the rationale for selecting a quantitative, non-experimental, correlational, cross-sectional approach. The chapter then details the procedures for participant selection and sampling, describes the development and administration of the questionnaire used for data collection, and explains the statistical techniques applied to analyze the data. In addition, it defines the key variables and addresses the assumptions, limitations, and delimitations of the research design. Finally, the chapter discusses the ethical safeguards implemented to ensure participant confidentiality and anonymity.

Research Methodology and Design

This study employed a quantitative research methodology, grounded in the belief that measurable data can reveal meaningful patterns and relationships between variables in real-world settings (House, 2018; Park et al., 2020). Quantitative methods allow researchers to apply statistical tools to numerical data, examine relationships between constructs, and rigorously test hypotheses (House, 2018; Park & Park, 2016).

This approach aligns with Deweyan pragmatism, which underpins the study's philosophical stance. Pragmatism emphasizes practical inquiry and the generation of actionable knowledge to address contemporary social challenges (Brown, 2009). Given the study's goal, to identify factors that act as proxies for eco-anxiety and explore their relationship with employee

engagement in private companies, a quantitative methodology was deemed the most appropriate. Guided by this instrumentalist perspective, the quantitative study aims to generate findings that are both relevant and applicable (Yilmaz, 2013). Additionally, the quantitative approach allows for the analysis of individual responses across large populations, supporting generalization and enabling the identification of potential cause-and-effect relationships (Savela, 2018). Because this study aimed to explore variable relationships within a broad, non-localized population, the quantitative method was particularly well-suited.

Alternative approaches were considered but ultimately rejected in favor of quantitative methods. Qualitative research, for example, emphasizes subjective interpretation over statistical analysis (Yilmaz, 2013). As Rutberg and Bouikidis (2018) note, qualitative methods are ideal for exploring complex phenomena such as lived experiences, group dynamics, or behavioral processes. These often involve in-depth interviews, observations, or narrative analysis to uncover meaning and context. While this approach yields rich, nuanced insights, it is not designed for quantifying variable relationships or testing specific hypotheses (Rutberg & Bouikidis, 2018). Because the present study sought to identify measurable indicators of eco-anxiety and assess their statistical correlation with employee engagement, qualitative methods were insufficient to meet its objectives.

A mixed methods approach, which integrates qualitative and quantitative techniques, was also evaluated. Mixed methods are valuable for capturing complex social phenomena and enhancing validity through methodological triangulation (Harkiolakis, 2021; Rutberg & Bouikidis, 2018; Schoonenboom, 2018). However, this approach was not adopted as the research didn't aim to develop or extend theory through triangulation but to confirm specific hypotheses

about the relationship between eco-anxiety and employee engagement. Thus, a qualitative component was not necessary (Harkiolakis, 2021; Rutberg & Bouikidis, 2018).

Within the broader methodological framework, this study employed a non-experimental, correlational, and cross-sectional design to examine the statistical relationship between eco-anxiety and employee engagement. Correlational research is well-suited for assessing the strength and direction of associations between naturally occurring variables without manipulating them (Harkiolakis, 2021). The aim was not to establish causality but to identify variables that may serve as proxies for eco-anxiety and be linked to lower engagement in private-sector contexts.

A non-experimental approach was appropriate, given the study's focus on pre-existing psychological states within real-world organizational settings. Introducing experimental manipulation could have compromised both the authenticity of responses and the ecological validity of the findings (Gray, 2022; Podsakoff & Podsakoff, 2019). Additionally, ethically, it would be problematic to induce or alleviate eco-anxiety among employees, as such interventions might cause psychological distress or workplace disruption, violating research ethics related to human participants.

The cross-sectional design further supported the study's objective by capturing the current state of eco-anxiety and employee engagement without exploring changes over time (Gray, 2022; Harkiolakis, 2021). While a longitudinal approach could provide insights into temporal dynamics, the research questions were concerned with present-moment associations, making a single time-point data collection both appropriate and sufficient.

Alternative research designs were considered but ultimately deemed unsuitable. Experimental and quasi-experimental designs, which involve variable manipulation and random

assignment, were incompatible with the study's goals. Inducing changes in eco-anxiety or engagement not only poses ethical risks (Gray, 2022) but also undermines the study's intent to explore natural variation. Similarly, causal-comparative and comparative designs, which infer causation or assess differences between predetermined groups, did not align with the correlational focus of this research (Harkiolakis, 2021).

In summary, the study employed a quantitative, non-experimental, correlational, and cross-sectional design, carefully chosen to align with its purpose and hypotheses. This approach enabled the statistical analysis of relationships between eco-anxiety and employee engagement without altering natural settings. It offered a structured, evidence-based framework to identify factors that may contribute to low engagement in private companies, thereby advancing understanding in the areas of mental health and workplace sustainability.

Population and Sample

The targeted population for this quantitative, non-experimental, correlational, and cross-sectional study consisted of private-sector employees who are currently employed, aged 18 years or older and experiencing some level of eco-anxiety. Given the purpose of the study, to identify factors that serve as proxies for eco-anxiety and contribute to lowering employee engagement in private companies, this population was appropriate, as it provided access to working individuals who may be experiencing the psychological effects of environmental concerns in professional contexts. Employee engagement is a workplace phenomenon specific to actively employed individuals, and eco-anxiety has been increasingly recognized as a relevant issue among workforce populations worldwide (Cosh et al., 2024; Niedzwiedz & Katikireddi, 2023). Including participants regardless of geographic location helped account for varying regional

experiences with climate change and organizational practices, while also supporting the potential generalizability of results to multinational private companies (Awasthi et al., 2025).

The study used a non-probabilistic purposive sampling method, which allows researchers to intentionally select participants based on specific demographic characteristics that are relevant to the research problem. This approach not only ensures the collection of meaningful data but also enables the expansion of the participant pool through referrals (Harkiolakis, 2021).

Purposive sampling is particularly valuable when certain individuals, events, or settings are chosen because they are known to offer critical insights that other sampling methods may not capture (Maxwell, 2008). The specific inclusion criteria for this study were as follows: participants must be (a) currently employed, (b) at least 18 years old, (c) experiencing some level of eco-anxiety, (d) working in the private sector. Given the specificity of the study and its focus on workplace engagement and psychological responses to environmental concerns, these criteria ensured that participants could provide insight into the constructs being measured. To further increase sample diversity and reduce potential selection bias, a snowball sampling technique was employed (Atkinson & Flint, 2001). Qualified participants were encouraged to share the study with colleagues, thereby expanding the sample across multiple organizations and geographic regions.

Participants were recruited via several professional and social media platforms, including LinkedIn, Facebook, Instagram, and Slack. Recruitment posts contained a call for participation and a link to the online questionnaire, hosted on SurveyMonkey (SurveyMonkey, n.d.). These platforms enabled the researcher to access a broad and varied participant pool while maintaining control over inclusion criteria through the survey's screening questions. Participation was

voluntary and anonymous, and informed consent was required before participants could begin the survey.

An a priori power analysis was conducted using G* Power 3.1.9.7 (Faul et al., 2007, 2009) to determine the minimum required sample size for a bivariate correlation analysis. The analysis employed an exact test using the bivariate normal model. Based on Cohen's (1988) guidelines, a medium effect size ($r = .30$) was selected as a reasonable estimate for the expected correlation strength in psychological research. With a significance level (α) of .05 and a desired statistical power of .95, the analysis indicated that a minimum of 138 participants would be required to detect a statistically significant correlation (Figure 2). While Bujang (2024) recommends a minimum of 149 participants based on confidence interval precision for a moderate effect size, the current study followed a power-based approach, which is suitable for hypothesis testing purposes. By adhering to these parameters, the study followed methodological guidelines for sample size determination in correlational research designs, emphasizing power-based planning over heuristic rules (Bujang, 2024; Hanley, 2016).

Figure 2

*Two-Tailed Model ($p = 0.05$) from G*Power Analysis*

The final sample included 138 participants, thereby meeting the minimum threshold established by the power analysis and supporting the robustness of the statistical analysis conducted. The use of purposive and snowball sampling, along with a widely distributed online survey, facilitated access to participants with diverse demographic and occupational characteristics, contributing to the breadth of perspectives and reduced bias captured, though with limitations to external validity due to the non-random nature of the sampling methods. (Atkinson & Flint, 2001).

Materials/Instrumentation

A survey instrument was employed to collect data for this study. Specifically, a self-administered questionnaire was used (see Appendix A), which was designed to identify factors that serve as proxies for eco-anxiety and contribute to lowering employee engagement in private

companies. A questionnaire is a commonly used data collection instrument in which each participant responds to an identical set of questions presented in a predetermined order (de Vaus, 2014; Ekinci, 2015). This method is particularly well-suited for large-scale studies that are geographically dispersed (Gray, 2022). Questionnaires are most effective when they contain standardized questions that are likely to be interpreted consistently by all respondents, making them especially appropriate for descriptive research (Robson & McCartan, 2016). One advantage of self-administered questionnaires is the reduced likelihood that respondents will tailor their answers to please the researcher or to align with perceived social norms (Dillman et al., 2014).

The questionnaire was divided into six sections. The first section included seven demographic questions related to the participants themselves, their professional background, their organization, and their role within it. The specific demographic factors chosen were informed by their relevance in prior research and aligned with the study's central research question (Abrahamse & Steg, 2009; Dumont et al., 2016; Niedzwiedz & Katikireddi, 2023). In the second section, participants self-reported their levels of eco-anxiety, followed by a third section where they evaluated their engagement at work. The fourth section examined psychological factors aligned with the study's hypotheses, with each factor represented by a single question. Similarly, the fifth section addressed organizational factors, and the sixth and final section focused on socio-environmental factors. Across the last three sections, a total of 12 questions were designed to capture the key elements linked to eco-anxiety and their potential role in reducing employee engagement in private companies. In total, the questionnaire consisted of 21 questions. The first version of the questionnaire was developed based on the research questions and the twelve hypotheses of the study, supported by the extant literature.

In social science research, Likert-type scales are commonly used to measure attitudes and perceptions in an ordinal format (Harkiolakis, 2025). This study employed a 7-point Likert scale, ranging from “Strongly Disagree” to “Strongly Agree,” to capture greater granularity in participants’ responses. Compared to a 5-point scale, the 7-point format offers improved sensitivity and reliability, which is particularly important for capturing nuanced psychological constructs such as eco-anxiety and employee engagement (DeVellis, 2017; Finstad, 2010; Preston & Colman, 2000). The inclusion of a neutral midpoint allows respondents to express ambivalence or uncertainty, which is particularly important when exploring complex and emotionally charged topics, such as those represented by the study’s hypotheses (DeVellis, 2017; Harkiolakis, 2025).

The initial draft of the questionnaire was reviewed by a panel of experts. Prof. Dr. Nicholas Harkiolakis from École des Ponts Business School in Paris, France, acted as a methodology expert. Jennifer Uchendu acted as subject matter expert. She is the founder of SustyVibes, a youth-led organization advancing sustainability advocacy, and the eco-anxiety Africa project (TEAP), an initiative dedicated to understanding and addressing eco-anxiety in African populations. Finally, Imogen Wall also acted as subject matter expert. She is a crisis management and mental health trainer and consultant. Their feedback was instrumental in shaping and refining the questionnaire, which subsequently informed a pilot study aimed at assessing the instrument’s relevance and validity. The pilot study was conducted, before large-scale distribution, with 10 participants, adhering to the recommended minimum of 10 participants for such studies (Fink, 2009). The objective of the pilot test was to ensure that respondents could answer the questions without difficulty and that the data could be collected reliably.

To increase the response rate among French-speaking participants, a French version of the questionnaire (Appendix B) was developed using the TRAPD method: translation, review, adjudication, pre-testing, and documentation (Vujcich et al., 2021). The translation was certified by Dr. Eric Bon, CEO of the Professional language services group, in-house counsel, court of appeal-accredited expert translator, conference interpreter, and fellow of the société des gens de lettres.

Operational Definitions of Variables

In this study, eco-anxiety serves as the key independent (predictor) variable, and employee engagement is the dependent (outcome) variable. In addition to these primary variables, twelve constructs were also examined as potential predictors of reduced engagement. Each variable in this study was measured with a single-item indicator using a 7-point Likert-type scale ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree), 2 (Disagree), 3 (Somewhat Disagree), 4 (Neither Agree nor Disagree), 5 (Somewhat Agree), 6 (Agree), and 7 (Strongly Agree). Higher values on each item indicate stronger perceptions or intensities of the construct in question. It is assumed here that Likert-type response categories approximate interval-level measurement. Although the interval nature of individual items is debated, the summed scale score may still be treated as interval-level, as summation can mitigate the impact of violations of the interval assumption at the item level (Jamieson, 2004; Norman, 2010). Below, each variable is defined operationally.

Eco-anxiety (FeelWorried). Labeled as “FeelWorried”, this variable was defined as the anxiety individuals experience due to concerns about environmental degradation and climate change (Pihkala, 2022b). It was the primary independent (predictor) ordinal variable, mapping directly to the central research question regarding reduced employee engagement. It was assessed by survey question Q1.

Employee Engagement (FeelEngaged). Labeled as “FeelEngaged”, this variable was defined as the integration of individuals’ selves into their work roles, encompassing physical, cognitive, and emotional aspects (Kahn, 1990). It was the dependent (outcome) ordinal variable, mapping directly to the study’s central research question. It was assessed by survey question Q2.

Lack of Control (LittleControl). Labeled as “LittleControl” this variable was defined as the feeling of personal powerlessness when confronting large-scale ecological crises (Hickman et al., 2021; Pihkala, 2020). It was an independent ordinal variable mapping to hypothesis H1. It was assessed by survey question Q3.

Cognitive Dissonance (ValueConflicts). Labeled as “ValueConflicts”, this variable referred to the psychological discomfort that occurs when holding contradictory beliefs, ideas, or values, such as when environmental awareness conflicts with unsustainable behaviors (Festinger, 1957; Gifford, 2011). It was an independent ordinal variable mapping to hypothesis H2. It was assessed by survey question Q4.

Emotional Exhaustion (FeelExhausted). Labeled as “FeelExhausted”, this variable was defined as the persistent state of physical and emotional exhaustion caused by high work and personal demands and a lack of sufficient emotional support, including climate-change-related stressors (Jin et al., 2020; Pihkala, 2020). It was an independent ordinal variable mapping to hypothesis H3. It was assessed by survey question Q5.

Chronic Stress (StressLowersEngagement). Labeled as “StressLowersEngagement” this variable was defined as the persistent mental health difficulties caused by prolonged exposure to climate-related stressors (Hickman et al., 2021). It was an independent ordinal variable mapping to hypothesis H4. It was assessed by survey question Q6.

Low Well-being (WellbeingTreat). Labeled as “WellbeingTreat”, this variable was defined as the negative condition that individuals and societies can experience (World Health Organization, 2022). It was an independent ordinal variable mapping to hypothesis H5. It was assessed by survey question Q7.

Lack of Corporate Sustainability Initiatives (LackOfSustainability). Labeled as “LackOfSustainability”, this variable was defined as the absence of meaningful actions addressing social and environmental responsibility (Glavas & Kelley, 2014). It was an independent ordinal variable mapping to hypothesis H6. It was assessed by survey question Q8.

Company Purpose Statement without Reference to Sustainability (PurposeStatement). Labeled as “PurposeStatement”, this variable was defined as the lack of the organization’s ambition to effect positive change with reference to sustainability and provide employees with a profound sense of significance (Quinn & Thakor, 2018). It was an independent ordinal variable mapping to hypothesis H7. It was assessed by survey question Q9.

Absence of Employee Green Behaviors (AbsenseOfEngagement). Labeled as “AbsenseOfEngagement”, this variable was defined as the absence of quantifiable employee behaviors that support environmental sustainability goals at work (Ones & Dilchert, 2012). It was an independent ordinal variable mapping to hypothesis H8. It was assessed by survey question Q10.

Perceived Lack of Leadership Support (LackOfLeadership). Labeled as “LackOfLeadership”, this variable was defined as the employee perception that leaders are not committed to or do not actively promote sustainability efforts (Robertson & Barling, 2017). It was an independent ordinal variable mapping to hypothesis H9. It was assessed by survey question Q11.

Media Exposure (MediaPresentations). Labeled as “MediaPresentations” this variable was defined as the stress caused by alarming media coverage of environmental issues (Niedziedz & Katikireddi, 2023). It was an independent ordinal variable mapping to hypothesis H10. It was assessed by survey question Q12.

Uncertainty Regarding Environmental Regulations (Uncertainty). Labeled as “Uncertainty”, this variable was defined as the unpredictable policies that reduce environmental concern (Lu, 2024). It was an independent ordinal variable mapping to hypothesis H11. It was assessed by survey question Q13.

Perceived Environmental Regulatory and Market Pressure (Regulations). Labeled as “Regulations”, this variable was defined as the institutional forces, such as regulations and market expectations, that influence stakeholders’ engagement in sustainability efforts (Bansal & Roth, 2000). It was an independent ordinal variable mapping to hypothesis H12. It was assessed by survey question Q14.

Before answering the subject matter questions, participants were asked to provide demographic information to support descriptive and subgroup analyses. Occupation (D1) and employment sector (D2) were treated as nominal categorical variables, collected through open-ended responses to contextualize participants’ work roles and industries. Organization size (D3) was measured using a categorical variable with four options: Micro-sized (<10 employees), Small-sized (10–49), Medium-sized (50–249), and Large-sized (250+). Company sustainability purpose (D4) was a binary variable (Yes/No) assessing whether the organization’s stated purpose reflects a commitment to environmental or social responsibility. Age group (D5) was treated as an ordinal categorical variable, with participants selecting from four ordered age ranges: 24 and below, 25–54, 55–64, and 65 and over. Country of residence (D6) was treated as a nominal

categorical variable, captured through an open-text field to identify the geographic distribution of participants. Gender identity (D7) was treated as a nominal categorical variable, with participants selecting from four options: Female, Male, Non-binary or other (with a write-in option), and Prefer not to say. These demographic variables were selected based on their relevance in prior research and their potential to influence eco-anxiety and employee engagement outcomes.

Data Collection and Analysis

Participant recruitment was conducted through a call for participation posted on social media platforms (Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, Slack) and disseminated via my professional networks. Individuals who met the criteria: (a) currently employed in the private sector, (b) at least 18 years old, and (c) experiencing some level of eco-anxiety, were invited to participate. In addition, a snowball sampling strategy (Atkinson & Flint, 2001) encouraged respondents to share the survey with other qualified contacts. To enhance response rates, an introductory message was included with the questionnaire, in line with recommendations by Dillman et al. (2014), who emphasize the importance of such messages in encouraging participation. Additionally, the introduction served as a pre-screening and informed consent mechanism by clearly specifying the intended target group for the study, following guidelines by Dillman (2014).

Data were collected through an online questionnaire developed and hosted on SurveyMonkey (SurveyMonkey, n.d.). Compared to paper-based surveys, online questionnaires are more cost-effective, can be modified quickly, and automatically store results, thereby simplifying data handling and minimizing errors (Singh & Sagar, 2021). In addition, a web-based questionnaire allowed completion rate tracking (Gray, 2022). The online form remained active until the minimum number of completed questionnaires was reached. Once the survey closed, the raw data were exported in a spreadsheet format for cleaning and further analysis.

In total, 182 responses were obtained, aligning with the minimum sample size recommended by the a priori power analysis conducted in G*Power 3.1.9.7 (Faul et al., 2007, 2009). In line with ethical recommendations (Crow et al., 2007; Gray, 2022), no personally identifiable information was collected.

After data collection closed, the raw dataset was downloaded from SurveyMonkey in comma-separated values (CSV) format. Data were inspected for missing values, outliers, and any inconsistencies (Altman & Krzywinski, 2016; Pallant, 2020). Cases failing to meet inclusion criteria were excluded. Demographic data were coded to facilitate statistical analysis. Age was treated as an ordinal categorical variable coded “1” for 24 and below, “2” for 25–54, “3” for 55–64, and “4” for 65 and over. Organization size was coded “1” for micro (<10 employees), “2” for small (10–49), “3” for medium (50–249), and “4” for large (250+). Gender identity was categorized as “1” for female, “2” for male, “3” for non-binary/other, and “4” for prefer not to say. Country of residence was captured as an open-ended response; afterward, countries were grouped by continent or region for exploratory comparisons when sample sizes allowed. Additional variables (e.g., role, company sustainability purpose) were each assigned a numeric code (1/0) or an ordinal code where applicable.

The 7-point Likert-type responses for the study’s main variables (e.g., eco-anxiety, employee engagement, and the twelve factors) were similarly coded, with “Strongly Disagree” as 1 and “Strongly Agree” as 7. The final dataset contained no patterns of systematically missing data that would compromise the interpretability of the results. All data were then imported into SPSS version 29 software (IBM, 2024) for subsequent analyses. SPSS is widely used in social science research for its robust analytical capabilities and user-friendly interface that does not require programming expertise (Pallant, 2020).

Data analysis involved both descriptive and inferential statistical techniques. Descriptive statistics summarized demographic characteristics (e.g., age, gender, organization size) and key study variables, using measures of central tendency and variability (Harkiolakis, 2025; Pallant, 2020). Interval variables were assessed for normality via Q–Q plots and the Shapiro–Wilk test (Harkiolakis, 2025; Pallant, 2020). Non-normal variables underwent square root or log10 transformations; if normality remained unmet, non-parametric methods (e.g., Spearman’s rank-order correlation) were used (Harkiolakis, 2025; Pallant, 2020). Inferential analyses tested the study’s hypotheses and twelve research questions, examining links between psychological, organizational, and socio-environmental factors related to eco-anxiety and employee engagement. Pearson’s correlations were used for normally distributed variables, and Spearman’s for non-normal ones (Harkiolakis, 2025; Pallant, 2020). To assess predictive effects, simple and multiple linear regressions evaluated whether eco-anxiety predicted engagement, controlling for demographics (Harkiolakis, 2025; Pallant, 2020). Moderation analyses with interaction terms explored whether contextual factors altered this relationship (Harkiolakis, 2025). Post hoc tests (e.g., one-way ANOVA, Kruskal–Wallis H) examined demographic influences on eco-anxiety and engagement levels (Harkiolakis, 2025; Pallant, 2020). By integrating both descriptive and inferential methods, the analysis provided a comprehensive view of how eco-anxiety and related factors affect employee engagement in private-sector settings.

Assumptions

This study was based on several assumptions, understood as conditions accepted as true without direct proof (Ellis & Levy, 2009). The study is grounded in a pragmatic paradigm, which supports a functional and consequence-driven approach to knowledge (Brown, 2009). As such, it is assumed that truth and meaning are constructed through practical engagement with the world,

and thus, the knowledge generated through this research is both useful and action-oriented. The assumption here is not of absolute objectivity, as in positivism, but of intersubjective agreement regarding the empirical patterns observed (Harkiolakis, 2025).

It was assumed that the quantitative, non-experimental, correlational, and cross-sectional design was appropriate for the research objectives. It was further assumed that the variables were measurable through the developed online questionnaire and that the instrument accurately captured the constructs of interest. Participants were assumed to understand the survey language and terminology, particularly concepts such as "eco-anxiety" and "employee engagement," and responded honestly and thoughtfully.

It was assumed that the purposive recruitment approach via social media yielded a sample that is both adequate in size and reasonably representative of the broader target population, within the constraints of non-probability sampling. Moreover, it was assumed that the collected data were accurately processed and analyzed using SPSS software, and that the statistical methods applied, descriptive and inferential, were appropriate for addressing the study's research questions and hypotheses.

Finally, this study assumed that the observed relationships, while identified in a specific, voluntary, and online-recruited sample, have implications for similar populations working in private organizations, especially within contexts where environmental concerns may be salient. This assumption aligns with the pragmatic goal of generating actionable insights that contribute to addressing real-world organizational challenges (Brown, 2009; Harkiolakis, 2025).

Limitations

Limitations in a study are potential weaknesses that researchers identify but often lie outside their direct control, and they must be acknowledged for their possible impact on results

(Creswell & Creswell, 2018; Ellis & Levy, 2009). One limitation here is the reliance on a quantitative, non-experimental, correlational, and cross-sectional design. While correlational methods capture the strength and direction of naturally occurring relationships, they cannot establish causality (Gray, 2022; Harkiolakis, 2025). Further, the cross-sectional nature confines the analysis to a single point in time, preventing insights into how eco-anxiety and employee engagement might change over longer periods (Gray, 2022).

Another limitation stems from using single-item indicators for eco-anxiety, employee engagement, and the twelve hypothesized predictors. Although such measures streamline data collection and lower respondent burden, they do not offer the same level of reliability and validity as multi-item scales (DeVellis, 2017). This challenge is compounded by the self-administered survey format, which raises the possibility of common method bias when the same individual provides data for both predictor and outcome variables (Bailey et al., 2017). To mitigate these issues, the questionnaire was reviewed by experts, pilot tested, and administered anonymously to reduce conformity pressures (Creswell & Creswell, 2018).

Sample-related constraints also limit the study's external validity. Because participants volunteered, possibly skewing the sample toward those more concerned about environmental issues, a snowball sampling technique was employed to broaden participation and reduce selection bias (Atkinson & Flint, 2001). Despite administering the survey in both English and French, and taking into account context effects that language differences can introduce (Schuman et al., 1981), the findings may still fall short of fully reflecting the breadth of cultural, linguistic, or organizational nuances.

Finally, relying solely on quantitative methods means the study cannot uncover the deeper, contextual insights that qualitative or mixed approaches might reveal (Creswell &

Creswell, 2018). Although the numerical data provide useful patterns, they do not illuminate the underlying motivations or lived experiences shaping eco-anxiety and engagement. Future research could incorporate interviews or ethnographic methods to enrich these findings and deepen our understanding of eco-anxiety in real-world organizational settings.

Delimitations

Delimitations specify those aspects or factors the researcher intentionally leaves out of the study, thereby defining its boundaries and limiting the scope of its findings (Ellis & Levy, 2009). The primary delimitation of this study is its choice to employ a quantitative, non-experimental, correlational, and cross-sectional design instead of a qualitative or mixed-methods approach. By relying on numerical data and statistical analysis, the study focuses on measuring the strength and direction of relationships between eco-anxiety and employee engagement, leaving out the nuanced contextual insights that could be gained through qualitative inquiry (Yilmaz, 2013).

A second delimitation pertains to the study's population and sample. Only currently employed adults (age 18 or above) who self-identify as experiencing eco-anxiety were included, thereby excluding individuals in the public or nonprofit sectors as well as those not reporting eco-anxiety. The sample was further limited to English and French speakers, which excludes perspectives of non-English/French speakers. Finally, the study employed single-item indicators for eco-anxiety and employee engagement, along with 12 hypothesized predictors, thus narrowing its scope. Moreover, the cross-sectional design focuses on present associations instead of capturing how eco-anxiety and engagement evolve over time (Gray, 2022).

Ethical Assurances

Throughout the research process, ethical considerations were rigorously upheld. The risk to participants was minimal, as the study posed no foreseeable harm and involved no sensitive or intrusive questions. The study did not induce stress beyond that encountered in normal daily life. Participation was entirely voluntary, and informed consent was obtained from all participants before data collection (Wiles et al., 2007). Participants were provided with clear information about the purpose and scope of the study, their right to withdraw at any point without consequence, and the measures taken to protect their anonymity.

To preserve confidentiality, no personally identifiable information was collected, and responses were anonymized upon submission. All data were stored securely in password-protected files on an encrypted device, with access limited solely to me (Crow et al., 2007). This approach ensured that participants' identities remained protected and their privacy respected. The ethical protocols employed throughout the study supported the safeguarding of participants' rights at every stage (Gray, 2022).

Summary

This study used a quantitative approach to explore the relationship between eco-anxiety and employee engagement in private companies. A non-experimental, correlational, and cross-sectional design was chosen to examine statistical associations between variables without manipulating conditions or introducing interventions. The primary aim was to identify factors that act as proxies for eco-anxiety and to assess their potential impact on employee engagement.

Participants were recruited using purposive and snowball sampling methods, targeting currently employed adults in the private sector who self-identified as experiencing some level of eco-anxiety. Recruitment took place online through social and professional media platforms. A

total of 182 participants completed an anonymous, self-administered online questionnaire consisting of seven demographic questions and 14 items aligned with the study's hypotheses.

Twelve independent variables were identified as potential proxies for eco-anxiety. These variables represented diverse psychological, organizational, and socio-environmental factors and collectively formed the study's key predictor variable. The primary outcome, or dependent variable, was employee engagement. Each variable was measured using a single-item indicator rated on a 7-point Likert scale, allowing for the capture of nuanced psychological and organizational perceptions. To ensure the questionnaire's clarity, relevance, and reliability, it was reviewed by subject matter experts and piloted before distribution. A French version was also developed using a rigorous translation protocol to enhance accessibility.

Data were cleaned, coded, and analyzed using IBM SPSS (version 29). Descriptive statistics were used to summarize participant demographics and key study variables. Normality tests guided the choice of statistical methods; depending on data distribution, both parametric (Pearson's correlation) and non-parametric (Spearman's correlation) analyses were conducted. Additionally, regression and moderation analyses were performed to test the study's hypotheses and to evaluate the predictive relationship between eco-anxiety and employee engagement, controlling for relevant demographic variables.

The study also considered underlying assumptions, acknowledged its limitations and delimitations, and detailed the ethical considerations that informed its design and implementation. This methodological framework forms the basis for the next chapter, which presents the study's findings and examines the statistical relationships between eco-anxiety and employee engagement within the private sector.

Chapter 4: Findings

The purpose of this study was to examine the relationship between eco-anxiety and employee engagement within private companies, with particular attention to the psychological, organizational, and socio-environmental factors that may serve as proxies for eco-anxiety and contribute to workplace disengagement. This chapter presents the findings derived from the quantitative, non-experimental, correlational, and cross-sectional research design outlined in Chapter 3. Data were collected via an online questionnaire distributed to private-sector employees who self-identified as experiencing eco-anxiety. A total of 182 clear responses were received, improving the alpha value to $\alpha = 0.03$. The responses were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistical methods.

This chapter begins by establishing the validity and reliability of the survey instrument. It then presents the study's results, starting with participant demographics, followed by tests for normality and inferential analyses. The findings are subsequently interpreted in relation to the research questions. The chapter concludes with a discussion of the results in the context of the theoretical framework and a summary of the key outcomes.

Validity and Reliability of the Data

Establishing the validity and reliability of the data is essential for ensuring the trustworthiness and interpretability of research findings (Gray, 2022). In quantitative studies, validity refers to the degree to which an instrument accurately measures what it intends to measure, while reliability relates to the consistency and replicability of the measurement process (DeVellis, 2017; Harkiolakis, 2025).

This study emphasizes construct validity, which reflects how well the questionnaire measures the theoretical construct of eco-anxiety as it relates to employee engagement (DeVellis,

2017; Harkiolakis, 2025). Construct validity was addressed through both content and criterion validity procedures. The development of questionnaire items was grounded in a robust theoretical framework supported by the literature (Harkiolakis, 2025). To enhance content validity, the questionnaire underwent expert review by subject matter. This process ensured the relevance, clarity, and alignment of each item with the theoretical constructs under investigation. Following the expert review, a pilot study was conducted to assess the instrument's clarity, coherence, and usability. Although internal validity, defined as the degree to which causal relationships can be inferred (Andrade, 2018), is often a focus in experimental designs, it was not a central concern in this correlational, cross-sectional study. Since the aim was to examine associations rather than causality, internal validity was not a primary requirement.

In contrast, external validity, or the generalizability of the findings, was of significant importance. Generalizability is influenced by sample representativeness and the context in which the data were collected (Gray, 2022). To optimize external validity, the study employed purposive and snowball sampling strategies to include a diverse group of eco-anxious employees from multiple countries and industries. Furthermore, a total of 182 participants were recruited, exceeding by 32% the minimum sample size of 138 participants estimated using G*Power analysis for detecting medium effect sizes at a 95% confidence level (Faul et al., 2007, 2009). This supports the adequacy of the sample for generalizing findings to similar populations of private-sector employees experiencing eco-anxiety.

Reliability in this study was assessed through internal consistency, a form of reliability that evaluates the extent to which items on a scale are interrelated and measure the same underlying construct (DeVellis, 2017; Harkiolakis, 2025). Among the three traditional forms of reliability: homogeneity, stability, and equivalence (Kirk & Miller, 1986), only homogeneity was

applicable, as the study used a single survey administration (ruling out stability testing) and only one version of the questionnaire (excluding the need for equivalence testing). Each of the 12 eco-anxiety variables was measured using a single item rated on a 7-point Likert scale. Because each construct was single-item, internal consistency reliability (Cronbach's α) could not be computed. Reliability was instead inferred from prior validation of these items in the literature and from their theoretical distinctiveness. Assuming a uni-dimensionality of the eco-anxiety construct (12 items loaded primarily on a single factor, Cronbach's α was calculated. The resulting alpha coefficient of .901 demonstrated excellent internal consistency. This indicates that the items used in the study were highly intercorrelated and likely measured a common underlying construct associated with eco-anxiety in the workplace.

Together, these steps demonstrate that the data collection instrument used in this study was both psychometrically sound and theoretically aligned with the constructs under investigation. The findings presented in this chapter can thus be interpreted with a high degree of confidence in their validity and reliability, within the limitations of a non-experimental research design.

Results

The dataset comprised responses from a total of 182 participants. The data captured from the questionnaire were exported to a csv file, coded where appropriate, and imported into IBM SPSS (version 29) for further statistical analysis. The majority of variables analyzed had a high response rate, with 177 valid responses recorded for each variable, representing 97.3% of the total sample. Only five cases (2.7%) were missing per variable, indicating minimal data loss. This consistency in data completeness across all measured constructs ensures a robust foundation

for subsequent statistical analyses, enhancing the reliability of the study's findings. A comprehensive presentation of the results can be found in Appendix C.

Company size was heavily skewed toward large firms, with 84.5% of participants from large organizations, 12.7% from medium-sized ones, and just 1.1% and 1.7% from micro and small enterprises. This likely results from the study's focus on eco-anxious professionals, as large firms more often engage in formal sustainability efforts that increase climate awareness. While this focus enhances relevance to large organizations, it limits generalizability to smaller firms with different sustainability dynamics.

Most participants held non-executive roles: 57.1% were employees, 22.5% managers, and 4.4% executives; 15.9% did not disclose their role. This mirrors typical hierarchies (Criscuolo et al., 2021), though managers and executives are slightly overrepresented (Gallup, 2024b), likely due to the focus on eco-anxious professionals, who often hold roles with greater responsibility. In job specialization, the largest group was "Other" (30.8%), followed by Analysts (17.0%) and Sales (17.0%). Admin/HR (11.5%) and Engineering (7.1%) were moderately represented, while Finance, Marketing, and Operations each accounted for less than 4%. Industry-wise, 37.4% worked in sustainability-related sectors, 24.2% in ICT, and 25.8% in "Other." Smaller shares came from Energy (6.0%), Finance (3.8%), and Consumer/Creative/Media (2.7%). The strong sustainability presence aligns with elevated eco-anxiety in that field (Climate Change Coaches, 2024). The sample leans toward knowledge work in mission-driven or tech-focused contexts, which may limit broader generalizability.

Geographically, the participants were located in 17 countries, grouped by region for analysis purposes. The regional distribution was concentrated in Europe (55.5%), followed by Africa (15.9%), North America (14.3%), Asia-Pacific (7.7%), and South America (2.7%). A

small fraction of participants (3.8%) did not report their region. While the Global South is represented in this study, the sample is dominated by participants from Europe, introducing a regional bias. Given that Europe is widely recognized as the most environmentally conscious continent, this imbalance may influence the perspectives reflected in the findings.

Regarding gender, the sample is skewed heavily towards females, with 72.0% identifying as female and 23.1% as male. A very small proportion identified as non-binary/other (0.5%) or chose not to answer (4.4%). The overrepresentation of women is a noteworthy characteristic of the sample and may reflect broader trends in participation in sustainability-related research and initiatives, where women are often more actively engaged.

For age, the majority (91.8%) were between 25 and 54 years old, with younger respondents (< 25 years) accounting for 7.1%, and only 1.1% falling in the 55–64 age bracket. The sample is uniformly mid-career, which provides a mature enough cohort for studying workplace engagement and eco-anxiety without the volatility often seen in younger or near-retirement workers. Finally, 86.7% of respondents indicated that the purpose of their company reflects a commitment to environmental or social responsibility, while only 13.3% did not, suggesting a generally purpose-aligned workforce within the sample. This is a limitation in the sense that the sample does not represent employees who work in an organization where the organizational purpose does not directly address environmental aspects.

Cross-tabulations and Pearson Chi-Square tests were used to examine associations between key demographic variables (gender, age, region, industry, occupation, and specialization). No significant associations were found between gender and age, region, occupation, or specialization, nor between age and region, industry, or occupation (all $p > .05$). However, age was significantly associated with specialization, $\chi^2(16, N = 182) = 30.84, p = .014$,

possibly reflecting typical career trajectories, such as younger participants in tech roles and older ones in administrative or strategic positions. A significant association was also found between gender and industry, $\chi^2(15, N = 182) = 25.39, p = .045$, suggesting gendered patterns in sector employment. Women in this sample were more represented in sustainability (n = 54), ICT (n = 30), and “Other” (n = 34) industries. This aligns with broader trends of women being more present in purpose-driven sectors and may contribute to the sample’s overall orientation toward environmental and social responsibility. All other associations, including those between region and industry, were non-significant ($p > .05$).

To assess the normality of all non-nominal variables, the Shapiro-Wilk test was conducted. The results indicated that none of the variables followed a normal distribution. To support these findings, P-P plots were examined for distributional shape, while box plots were used to identify potential outliers (Appendix C). Based on these results, all non-nominal variables were treated as non-parametric, with non-parametric methods and medians used due to their robustness to skew and suitability for ordinal data. The detailed results are available in Table 1.

Table 1

Results from Non-parametric Statistical Methods

Variable	Min	Q1	Median	Q3	Max	Mode
FeelEngaged	2	5	6	6	7	6
LittleControl	1	3	5	5	7	5
ValueConflicts	1	5	6	7	7	7
FeelExhausted	1	3	5	6	7	5
StressLowersEngagement	1	3	5	6	7	5
WellbeingTreat	1	4	5	6	7	5
LackOfSustainability	1	4	5	6	7	7
PurposeStatement	1	4	5	6	7	6
AbsenseOfEngagement	1	4	5	6	7	6

LackOfLeadership	1	4	5	6	7	6
MediaPresentations	1	2	4	5	7	2
Uncertainty	1	3	5	5	7	5
Regulations	1	2	2	4	7	2

The variable *FeelEngaged*, measuring employee engagement, also showed a median of 6, indicating that participants generally felt highly engaged in their work. The combination of high eco-anxiety and high engagement could be an indication of the complexity of their relationship and challenges the assumption that eco-anxiety necessarily reduces work engagement. Further research would be required to support the assertion.

For the psychological factors, the variable *LittleControl*, which measured perceived powerlessness regarding environmental issues, had a median of 5. This suggests that participants generally somewhat agreed that feeling a lack of control over ecological crises reduced their work engagement. It indicates that such helplessness may diminish a sense of agency, contributing to disengagement. The variable *ValueConflicts*, which measured the impact of dissonance between personal environmental values and company practices, had a median of 6 and mode of 7, indicating a skew toward stronger agreement than the median suggests. This skew suggests that while the central tendency is strong agreement, some small value outliers may pull the median slightly lower. Participants commonly saw such misalignments as harmful to their engagement, highlighting the importance of value alignment in sustaining motivation.

The variable *FeelExhausted*, measuring emotional exhaustion from eco-anxiety, had a median of 5. Participants somewhat agreed that this exhaustion reduced their engagement, indicating a moderate but noticeable impact of eco-anxiety-related fatigue on workplace performance. The variable *StressLowersEngagement*, measuring chronic climate-related stress, had a median of 5. This reflects moderate agreement that ongoing environmental stress

negatively impacts engagement. Though not extreme, this stressor appears to be a consistent part of participants' experiences. The variable *WellbeingTreat*, measuring the impact of environmental concerns on overall well-being, had a median of 5. This indicates participants recognized a link between their well-being and work engagement, supporting the idea that psychological health influences occupational outcomes.

Turning to organizational factors, the variable *LackOfSustainability* had a median of 5 and mode of 7, indicating a skew toward stronger perceptions of disengagement due to absent sustainability initiatives. This suggests some participants feel more strongly than the median implies, emphasizing the motivational potential of environmental responsibility. The variable *PurposeStatement*, which evaluated the impact of a company's failure to include sustainability in its purpose statement, also yielded a median of 5 and mode of 6, again indicating a skew toward stronger agreement. Respondents somewhat agreed that the lack of sustainability in a company's purpose statement reduced engagement, highlighting its symbolic importance.

AbsenceOfEngagement, measuring the lack of observable employee green behaviors within the organization, similarly returned a median of 5 and mode of 6, suggesting that while the central tendency reflects moderate agreement, some respondents felt more strongly disengaged due to this absence, pointing to the influence of peer modeling. *LackOfLeadership*, which captured perceptions of inadequate leadership support for environmental concerns, had a median of 5 and a mode of 6. This suggests a general tendency toward agreement, indicating that many participants perceived a lack of leadership support as a barrier to their engagement. However, the distribution also shows some lower-valued outliers, which may have influenced the central tendency and point to differing experiences among participants. Overall, these findings

underscore the importance of strong environmental leadership in cultivating a workplace culture that supports sustainability.

Among the socio-environmental variables, *MediaPresentations*, which measured the impact of media coverage of environmental crises, had a median of 4 and mode of 2, suggesting notable skewness with some participants finding media exposure more disengaging than the median reflects, possibly due to differences in coping styles, media literacy, or personal sensitivity. *Uncertainty*, referring to ambiguity around environmental regulations, showed a median of 5, indicating that participants somewhat agreed that such uncertainty reduced their engagement. This suggests that unclear policies may disrupt workplace expectations and weaken motivation. *Regulations*, which measured the impact of external regulatory or market pressures, had the lowest median (2), indicating general disagreement that such factors harm engagement. This suggests they may be seen as either necessary for sustainability or too remote to affect daily work. However, the interquartile range (IQR), defined as the difference between the first quartile (Q1) and the third quartile (Q3), is 2–4, suggesting that while the median perception is neutral, some participants rated the pressures as more disruptive. This spread points to minority views that may warrant further exploration.

To examine the impact of eco-anxiety and its related dimensions on employee engagement in private companies, one-sample Wilcoxon signed-rank tests were conducted for each variable. This non-parametric approach was selected due to the non-normal distribution of the data, and tested whether participants' median agreement levels for each item significantly differed from the neutral midpoint on the 7-point Likert scale (“Neither agree nor disagree”).

The Wilcoxon signed-rank tests revealed that participants significantly agreed with statements reflecting both eco-anxiety (*FeelWorried*, $p < .001$) and employee engagement

(*FeelEngaged*, $p < .001$), relative to the neutral midpoint of the Likert scale. This indicates that individuals in the sample reported experiencing worry, fear, or helplessness about environmental issues, while also maintaining a sense of engagement in their work. The co-occurrence of these two constructs suggests that eco-anxiety does not automatically result in disengagement. Instead, employees may remain involved and motivated at work despite their environmental concerns, underscoring the need to examine the specific factors: psychological, organizational, and socio-environmental, that influence how eco-anxiety impacts engagement.

To address the psychological factors (RQ1–RQ5 / H1–H5), five hypotheses (H1–H5) were tested to examine whether specific manifestations of eco-anxiety were associated with reduced employee engagement. Hypothesis H1₀ could not be rejected because the item *LittleControl* did not reach statistical significance ($p = .087$). As such, no conclusions can be drawn about the relationship between this particular variable and employee engagement. This non-significant finding may be attributable to characteristics of the sample or variability across contexts, and should therefore be explored further in future research.

In contrast, the null hypothesis for H2 was rejected ($p < .001$), indicating that cognitive dissonance, in the form of value conflicts between employees' environmental beliefs and organizational practices (*ValueConflicts*), is significantly associated with lower employee engagement. Rejection of the null hypothesis allows acceptance of the alternative hypothesis, suggesting that such dissonance contributes to workplace disengagement. This suggests that cognitive dissonance was both common among the sample population and linked to disengagement. Employees appear to feel demotivated when their workplace undermines or contradicts their environmental convictions.

The null hypothesis for H3 was also rejected ($p = .003$), demonstrating a statistically significant association between emotional exhaustion caused by eco-anxiety (*FeelExhausted*) and reduced employee engagement. This finding confirms that emotional exhaustion, a key symptom of psychological strain, is a salient factor through which eco-anxiety reduces individuals' ability to remain engaged and emotionally present in the workplace. Similarly, the null hypothesis for H4 (*StressLowersEngagement*) was rejected ($p = .003$), showing that chronic stress linked to climate concerns is significantly associated with reduced professional engagement. The data indicate that chronic, climate-related stress contributes to diminished workplace involvement, likely by draining mental and emotional resources needed for sustained performance.

Finally, H5₀ (*WellbeingTreat*) produced the strongest result among psychological variables, with the null hypothesis rejected ($p < .001$). This demonstrates that deteriorating well-being due to environmental concerns is perceived as a clear barrier to workplace engagement. Overall, four of the five null hypotheses for psychological factors were rejected (H2₀–H5₀), indicating that various internal dimensions of eco-anxiety are significantly associated with reduced engagement. The inability to reject H1₀ underscores the need for further research on the role, if any, of perceived control in shaping engagement.

To examine the organizational factors (RQ6–RQ9 / H6–H9), four hypotheses related to organizational factors were tested. For H6 (*LackOfSustainability*), the null hypothesis was rejected ($p < .001$). This suggests that a lack of visible corporate sustainability initiatives is significantly associated with lower employee engagement. This supports the idea that organizational inaction on environmental issues can exacerbate disengagement among environmentally concerned employees. The null hypothesis for H7 (*PurposeStatement*) was also

rejected ($p < .001$). This indicates that when a company's purpose statement does not reference environmental or social responsibility, it is perceived as misaligned with employees' values, and may result in disengagement. H8₀ (*AbsenseOfEngagement*) was similarly supported by the rejection of the null hypothesis ($p < .001$), revealing that the absence of green behaviors among colleagues or teams is significantly linked to reduced employee engagement. Visible environmental action in the workplace appears to foster stronger professional commitment. Finally, the null hypothesis for H9 (*LackOfLeadership*) was rejected ($p < .001$), demonstrating that perceived lack of leadership support for environmental issues significantly correlates with reduced engagement. This emphasizes the critical role that leadership plays in setting the tone for environmental responsibility and shaping how employees experience eco-anxiety in the workplace. Together, the findings for H6–H9 suggest that organizational culture and leadership behaviors are critical contextual factors that influence how eco-anxiety affects employee engagement.

To explore the socio-environmental factors (RQ10–RQ12 / H10–H12), three hypotheses were tested. For H10 (*MediaPresentations*), the null hypothesis was rejected ($p = .020$), indicating that media coverage of climate crises is perceived as a contributing factor to reduced engagement. This supports the idea that emotional or cognitive overload triggered by environmental media may interfere with employees' work focus. In contrast, the null hypothesis for H11 (*Uncertainty*) could not be rejected ($p = .066$), suggesting that uncertainty about environmental regulations does not show a consistent or statistically significant association with employee engagement. As such, no conclusions can be drawn about the alternative hypothesis, and this area remains open for future inquiry. However, the null hypothesis for H12₀ (*Regulations*) was rejected ($p < .001$), suggesting that perceived regulatory and market pressures

significantly impact employee engagement. When such pressures are experienced without sufficient organizational support, they may contribute to stress and disengagement.

Of the twelve hypotheses tested, ten null hypotheses were rejected, providing support for their corresponding alternative hypotheses. The two null hypotheses that could not be rejected (H_{10} and H_{110}) indicate areas where the data do not provide sufficient evidence for an association. Overall, the findings suggest that eco-anxiety is a multidimensional phenomenon influencing employee engagement through psychological experiences, organizational culture, and external pressures. These results offer a nuanced understanding of eco-anxiety's effects in private-sector contexts, while also highlighting the importance of leadership, alignment with sustainability values, and organizational response in mitigating disengagement risks.

To assess whether demographic factors significantly influenced the key psychological, organizational, and socio-environmental variables identified in this study. Non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis tests were used as an alternative to one-way ANOVA due to the non-normal distribution of variables.

Several statistically significant influences were found across geographic regions: For *ValueConflicts* ($H(df = 5, N = 182) = 25.49, p < .001$), there was a significant regional difference in how cognitive dissonance, due to conflicts between personal environmental values and company practices, affected engagement. Respondents from South America reported higher levels of value conflict compared to other regions, indicating potential underlying cultural or societal tensions. For the items *FeelExhausted* ($H(df = 5, N = 182) = 12.06, p = .034$), *StressLowersEngagement* ($H(df = 5, N = 182) = 11.72, p = .039$), and *WellbeingTreat* ($H(df = 5, N = 182) = 12.23, p = .032$), these psychological dimensions varied significantly by region. Participants from South America and Asia-Pacific reported higher median ranks, indicating

greater emotional exhaustion, chronic stress, and well-being impact due to eco-anxiety than those from Europe or North America. This is potentially due to greater exposure to environmental threats, socioeconomic vulnerabilities, and limited access to coping resources.

For the variables *LackOfSustainability* ($H(df = 5, N = 182) = 13.92, p = .016$), *PurposeStatement* ($H(df = 5, N = 181) = 15.59, p = .008$), *AbsenseOfEngagement* ($H(df = 5, N = 182) = 20.32, p = .001$), and *LackOfLeadership* ($H(df = 5, N = 182) = 20.64, p = .001$), the organizational factors showed significant variation by region. These findings suggest regional disparities in how organizational sustainability efforts, purpose alignment, and leadership support affect employee engagement under eco-anxiety. South American and Asia-Pacific participants again reported higher disengagement linked to these factors. This indicates that organizational shortcomings, such as unclear sustainability efforts, weak purpose alignment, and inadequate leadership, may have a stronger negative impact on employee engagement in South America and the Asia-Pacific, due to the local context previously described.

For the variable *Regulations* ($H(df = 5, N = 182) = 10.99, p = .052$), while marginally above the conventional threshold. This near-significant finding suggests regional variation in the perceived impact of regulatory and market pressures on engagement, warranting further investigation. The variable *WellbeingTreat* ($H(df = 3, N = 182) = 8.52, p = .036$) demonstrated statistical significance based on occupational role. There was a significant difference in the perceived impact of eco-anxiety on well-being by occupational status. Employees reported higher levels of distress than executives, suggesting that senior roles may offer a buffer or sense of detachment, possibly due to a stronger focus on company performance and survival.

While job specialization did not yield any statistically significant relationships at the conventional level ($p < .05$), several variables approached significance and may warrant attention

in future research. Specifically, the variable *StressLowersEngagement* ($H(df = 8, N = 182) = 14.44, p = .071$) demonstrated the closest result to significance, suggesting potential variation in how chronic climate-related stress influences engagement across specializations. Participants in marketing and operations reported higher disengagement levels due to stress, while participants in finance and production reported lower levels of stress-related disengagement.

Similarly, *Regulations* ($H(df = 8, N = 182) = 13.23, p = .104$), appeared neared significance. Respondents in marketing again showed higher disengagement, while finance professionals reported significantly lower levels, suggesting that roles closely aligned with financial performance and strategic priorities may be less affected. Variables such as *LittleControl*, and *ValueConflicts* also demonstrated p -values in the range of .132–.133, indicating meaningful variation trends that fell short of statistical significance but could be meaningful in applied contexts. These near-significant findings suggest that professional specialization may play a moderating role in the psychological and organizational experience of eco-anxiety, particularly in communication-intensive or strategic operational roles.

No statistically significant differences were observed across gender or age groups for any of the studied variables (all $p > .05$). This suggests that, within the current sample, gender and age did not meaningfully alter perceptions of eco-anxiety or its impact on employee engagement. Similarly, no significant differences were found across industries in any of the variables of interest (all $p > .05$).

The Kruskal-Wallis analysis revealed that geographic region, occupation, and to a lesser extent specialization, significantly influenced some key psychological and organizational variables, particularly concerning cognitive dissonance, emotional exhaustion, well-being, and perceived lack of sustainability support. These findings highlight the contextual nature of eco-

anxiety in the workplace, suggesting that regional, positional, and functional differences may moderate how environmental concerns affect employee engagement. Future research could explore these demographic disparities in greater depth, potentially using stratified sampling or qualitative follow-up to understand the lived experiences behind these statistical trends.

To better understand the relationship between eco-anxiety and employee engagement, and to unpack how psychological, organizational, and socio-environmental factors contribute to this dynamic, a Spearman's rho correlation analysis was conducted. This method was selected due to its appropriateness for ordinal Likert-scale data, particularly following the earlier detection of normality violations.

Within the psychological domain, several key patterns emerged. While *FeelEngaged* did not correlate significantly with value conflicts (*ValueConflicts*; $\rho = -.102, p = .171$), it demonstrated significant negative correlations with emotional exhaustion (*FeelExhausted*; $\rho = -.157, p = .035$) and diminished well-being (*WellbeingTreat*; $\rho = -.206, p = .005$). These results lend partial support to H3–H5 and also suggest that emotional exhaustion, well-being concerns, and perceived powerlessness may reflect a broader latent construct related to psychological eco-anxiety, potentially worth investigating further through exploratory factor analysis (EFA). An additional psychological factor was the perception of control. Although the earlier Wilcoxon test did not find a significant result for *LittleControl* (H1), the correlation analysis revealed a moderate negative relationship with engagement ($\rho = -.238, p = .001$). This suggests that, even though the broader group may have reported neutral perceptions of agency, individuals who felt powerless were more likely to report lower engagement, highlighting a significant subgroup dynamic.

Employees' perceptions of their organization's environmental integrity emerged as a critical determinant of engagement. Significant negative correlations were found between *FeelEngaged* and several organizational variables: *LackOfSustainability* ($\rho = -.150, p = .043$), *PurposeStatement* ($\rho = -.164, p = .028$), and *AbsenceOfEngagement* ($\rho = -.179, p = .016$). Additionally, *LackOfLeadership* trended in the negative direction ($\rho = -.142, p = .057$) but did not reach statistical significance. These findings support H6-H8, suggesting that when employees perceive their organizations as environmentally inactive or insincere, their engagement declines. Leadership support (H9), while trending negatively, may play a subtler or more context-dependent role.

The broader socio-environmental context yielded more mixed results. *Uncertainty* was significantly negatively correlated with engagement ($\rho = -.177, p = .017$), whereas media portrayals (*MediaPresentations*; $\rho = -.128, p = .086$) and perceptions of regulatory pressure (*Regulations*; $\rho = -.063, p = .399$) were not. Notably, H11 (*Uncertainty*) was not supported in earlier hypothesis testing, yet the correlation data suggests it may still play a role. This indicates that ambiguity in environmental policy can subtly erode employees' sense of security and purpose, diminishing engagement over time. Meanwhile, the effects of media narratives (H10) and perceived regulatory pressure (H12) may depend more on individual or contextual differences than on broad statistical trends.

This study aimed to address the central question: *What factors serve as proxies for eco-anxiety and contribute to reduced employee engagement in private companies?* The findings suggest that while eco-anxiety itself does not uniformly predict disengagement, its specific psychological, organizational, and socio-environmental manifestations are significantly associated with diminished employee engagement.

Of the twelve hypotheses tested, ten were statistically supported, with correlational analyses providing further confirmation. Psychological factors, especially emotional exhaustion, chronic stress, and reduced well-being, consistently emerged as key mediators of engagement. While *LittleControl* did not show a significant group-level effect, correlation analysis revealed a notable negative link to engagement, suggesting that perceived powerlessness increases disengagement risk. Organizational factors had a strong impact. Employees who perceived weak sustainability efforts, value misalignment, low peer engagement in green behaviors, or poor environmental leadership reported significantly lower engagement. These results point to organizational disillusionment, symbolic or operational, as a demotivating force. Socio-environmental influences were mixed. Participants acknowledged regulatory uncertainty and external pressure as stressors, but only regulatory uncertainty correlated meaningfully with engagement. Media exposure to environmental crises was significant in hypothesis testing but showed weak correlations, suggesting a complex or context-specific relationship.

Evaluation of the Findings

The findings support the conceptualization of eco-anxiety as a multidimensional stressor that influences key psychological conditions for employee engagement, consistent with Kahn's (1990) engagement theory and Lazarus and Folkman's (1984) transactional stress model. The findings also align with Boivin et al.'s (2025) unified framework, which defines eco-anxiety as a sociopsychological state driven by environmental threats and also perceived societal inaction. Four of five psychological hypotheses (H2–H5) were statistically supported, showing significant links between eco-anxiety, specifically value conflicts, emotional exhaustion, chronic stress, and low well-being, and reduced engagement. These results echo prior research on the mental health and occupational impacts of eco-anxiety (Ayassamy et al., 2024; Boluda-Verdú et al., 2022;

Pihkala, 2020). Notably, H5 (*WellbeingTreat*) received the strongest support, reinforcing that eco-anxiety can impair emotional availability, a condition essential for engagement (Kahn, 1990).

In contrast, H1 (*LittleControl*) was not statistically supported, despite prior studies connecting powerlessness to disengagement (Hickman et al., 2021). However, the negative correlation between lack of control and engagement suggests that some participants may still be affected, indicating individual variation. This aligns with findings that personal traits and coping styles mediate eco-anxiety outcomes (Bishop & Willis, 2014; Helm et al., 2018), and fits overall the study's theoretical framework (Figure 1).

All four organizational hypotheses (H6–H9) were supported, showing that weak sustainability practices, absence of a company purpose including sustainability, limited employee green behavior, and poor environmental leadership significantly reduce engagement. This aligns with the JD-R model (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007), which frames organizational resources as critical buffers against stress and disengagement. The strong support for H6 and H7 highlights how both visible sustainability actions and purpose statements serve as powerful symbols of shared values (Ayassamy et al., 2024; Glavas & Kelley, 2014). These results reinforce Kahn's (1990) claim that meaningfulness is key to engagement and echo findings that perceived inaction on environmental issues can foster disillusionment (Brooks & Greenberg, 2022).

Findings on socio-environmental factors were more mixed, reflecting their conceptual complexity (Brulle & Norgaard, 2019; Niedzwiedz & Katikireddi, 2023). H10 (*MediaPresentations*) was supported, indicating that climate crisis coverage can heighten eco-anxiety and hinder engagement due to emotional overload (Boluda-Verdú et al., 2022; Loll et al., 2023). While H11 (*Uncertainty*) was not statistically significant, its negative correlation with

engagement suggests that regulatory ambiguity may subtly erode psychological safety (Brooks & Greenberg, 2022; Kahn, 1990). Interestingly, H12 (*Regulations*) reached significance in hypothesis testing but not in correlation, implying that such pressures may reduce engagement under specific motivational conditions, consistent with Ernst et al. (2022).

Ten of the twelve hypotheses were statistically supported, with correlation analyses revealing nuanced, often indirect or subgroup-specific effects. These results reinforce the study's integrated framework (Figure 1), combining engagement theory (Kahn, 1990), the transactional stress model (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984), and the JD-R model (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007). Figure 3 presents the revised Eco-Anxiety and Workplace (Dis)Engagement (EWD) Framework, illustrating the psychological, organizational, and socio-environmental pathways through which eco-anxiety influences employee engagement. Solid arrows indicate relationships that were consistently supported by both hypothesis testing and correlational analysis. Among these pathways, psychological and organizational factors stood out as the most consistent predictors, emphasizing the central role of internal experience and workplace context in shaping how eco-anxiety impacts engagement.

Figure 3

Eco-Anxiety and Workplace (Dis)Engagement (EWD) Framework

The sample's gender and organizational demographics, predominantly women in large, sustainability-focused firms, reflect known patterns of higher eco-anxiety in such groups (Niedzwiedz & Katikireddi, 2023; Steinmann et al., 2023), though this limits generalizability to smaller firms. Including Global South participants enhances representativeness (Coffey et al., 2021). Addressing a key gap, the study provides rare empirical insight into the link between eco-anxiety and employee engagement (Ayassamy et al., 2024; Brooks & Greenberg, 2022). Crucially, eco-anxiety does not always reduce engagement; its impact depends on factors like perceived control, leadership support, and value alignment, supporting the view of eco-anxiety as both a risk and a motivator (Innocenti et al., 2023; Pihkala, 2020).

Summary

This chapter presented the findings of a quantitative, non-experimental study exploring the relationship between eco-anxiety and employee engagement within private companies. The data were collected from 182 eco-anxious employees across 17 countries and analyzed using descriptive, inferential, and correlational methods. The study confirmed strong validity and excellent reliability of the survey instrument, establishing confidence in the findings.

Demographic analysis showed the sample was predominantly mid-career, female, and employed in large, sustainability-oriented organizations. No significant differences in eco-anxiety or engagement were found across gender or age. However, regional and occupational differences influenced several key variables, particularly in South America and the Asia-Pacific, where participants reported higher eco-anxiety impacts.

Statistical testing supported 10 of 12 hypotheses. Psychological factors such as value conflicts, emotional exhaustion, chronic stress, and reduced well-being were significantly associated with lower engagement. Perceived lack of control was not statistically significant in hypothesis testing but showed a meaningful negative correlation with engagement. Organizational factors, including insufficient sustainability efforts, weak leadership support, and misalignment between company purpose and environmental values, were also strongly linked to disengagement. Socio-environmental influences produced mixed results. Media exposure and regulatory pressures were perceived as stressors, but only regulatory uncertainty showed a notable correlation with reduced engagement.

Correlation analysis further reinforced these findings, revealing that eco-anxiety's impact on engagement is shaped by individual perceptions and contextual workplace factors. The interpretation of results was guided by the integrated theoretical framework (Figure 1), which combined engagement theory, stress appraisal, and job demands-resources models. The findings offer strong support for the EWD framework (Figure 3), demonstrating that employee engagement is shaped by the interplay between individual psychological responses, organizational dynamics, and broader socio-environmental influences. Overall, the chapter highlights eco-anxiety as a multifaceted phenomenon. While it does not inherently reduce

engagement, its psychological, organizational, and contextual dimensions significantly influence how employees remain engaged at work.

Chapter 5: Implications for Management and Practice

This chapter explores the implications of the findings from Chapter 4 for management and practice, focusing on the underlying consequences of the relationships identified between eco-anxiety and employee engagement. The aim is to deepen understanding of how psychological, organizational, and socio-environmental factors act as proxies for eco-anxiety and influence engagement levels in private companies. The study addressed the central research question: *What factors serve as proxies for eco-anxiety and contribute to reduced employee engagement in private companies?* To explore this, 12 research questions were tested through a quantitative, cross-sectional, correlational design involving 182 participants.

In the psychological domain (RQ1–RQ5), the findings revealed that cognitive dissonance (RQ2), emotional exhaustion (RQ3), chronic stress (RQ4), and reduced well-being (RQ5) due to eco-anxiety are all significantly associated with lower employee engagement. Although lack of control over environmental issues (RQ1) was not statistically significant at the group level, correlational evidence suggests it may still matter for certain subgroups. Organizational factors (RQ6–RQ9) all four variables: lack of sustainability initiatives (RQ6), absence of sustainability in purpose statements (RQ7), lack of employee green behaviors (RQ8), and perceived leadership disengagement with environmental concerns (RQ9), were significantly linked to reduced engagement, underscoring the role of organizational culture and values. Socio-environmental factors (RQ10–RQ12) yielded more nuanced outcomes. Media exposure to climate crises (RQ10) and regulatory and market pressures (RQ12) were significantly associated with reduced engagement, while uncertainty about environmental regulations (RQ11) was not statistically significant in hypothesis testing but did show a negative correlation in further analyses.

Overall, these findings reveal that eco-anxiety is a complex, context-dependent phenomenon. While employee engagement was generally high, specific psychological and organizational conditions can erode professional motivation and connection. This chapter is structured in two sections: the first addresses implications for professional practice, focusing on how eco-anxiety shapes employee behavior and experience; the second discusses implications for policy and management, examining how organizational structures and external environments can amplify or buffer these effects.

Implications for professional practice

The study reveals that eco-anxiety significantly impacts employee engagement. Cognitive dissonance (RQ2), emotional exhaustion (RQ3), chronic stress (RQ4), and reduced well-being (RQ5) were all strongly linked to lower engagement. When employees experience internal conflict between their environmental values and their organization's actions, or when eco-anxiety drains emotional resources, their ability to stay engaged declines. These findings position eco-anxiety not only as an environmental or societal issue but as a psychological condition affecting workplace functioning. Its measurable presence among professionals indicates that emotional responses to climate degradation increasingly extend into the workplace.

Organizational culture plays a key role in how eco-anxiety influences engagement. Low engagement was associated with a lack of sustainability initiatives (RQ6), absent environmental values in company missions (RQ7), limited employee green behaviors (RQ8), and weak leadership support for environmental concerns (RQ9). When employees see their organizations as misaligned with their values, their sense of purpose erodes, reducing motivation. This implies that, for engagement to be effectively supported, sustainability is reflected not only in formal strategies but also in everyday practices and leadership behavior.

Socio-environmental influences also matter. Media exposure to climate crises (RQ10) was linked to lower engagement, suggesting that persistent exposure may overwhelm or distract employees. Perceived regulatory and market pressures (RQ12) showed a significant negative association with engagement, indicating that external stressors can spill over into organizational life.

Together, these findings support the study's central premise: eco-anxiety, through psychological, organizational, and external pathways, affects employee engagement, with tangible consequences for performance, decision-making, relationships, and retention.

Implications for policy and management

The findings show that eco-anxiety, as a multidimensional workplace stressor, has significant implications for organizational functioning and policy. Addressing the study's central concern, the results highlight how eco-anxiety can reduce employee engagement, particularly in large, sustainability-focused firms, posing risks to both individual well-being and organizational performance. Strategically, the concept of *employee engagement* may need to be redefined in the context of increasing climate-related stress.

Cognitive dissonance (RQ2), emotional exhaustion (RQ3), chronic stress (RQ4), and reduced well-being (RQ5) were all linked to lower engagement, suggesting that current mental health frameworks may overlook environmental stress as a legitimate psychosocial risk. The findings imply that eco-anxiety limits emotional availability, a key condition for engagement (Kahn, 1990), and point to a need for broader systemic supports. This raises questions about the adequacy of existing labor policies, especially in sustainability-driven sectors where value misalignment may be more pronounced. In such contexts, transparent sustainability reporting may influence how employees perceive organizational alignment, shaping their engagement.

All four organizational factors, absence of sustainability initiatives (RQ6), weak purpose (RQ7), lack of employee green behavior (RQ8), and insufficient leadership engagement with sustainability matters (RQ9), were significantly associated with lower engagement. These results suggest that engagement depends not only on job design or motivation, but also on perceived alignment between employees' environmental values and organizational practice. Sustainability emerges as a core part of organizational identity and culture. Leadership behavior and peer norms act as signals of shared values, with perceived value congruence potentially as influential as formal sustainability strategies in shaping engagement. This suggests that sustainability is not merely a compliance function, but is integral to organizational identity and culture.

Socio-environmental influences had more nuanced effects. Media exposure to climate crises (RQ10) was linked to lower engagement, indicating that external emotional stressors can affect focus and psychological safety. Perceived regulatory and market pressures (RQ12) were significant, showing how unmanaged external demands can impact employees' outlook and well-being. These findings point to the role of socio-environmental awareness in shaping how employees assess meaning, safety, and relevance in their roles, emphasizing the value of fostering organizational sensemaking.

Overall, the results position eco-anxiety as a systemic issue with tangible organizational and policy implications. The observed influence on employee engagement implies a significant connection to broader concerns of national well-being and mental health within climate adaptation strategies. Environmental stress, once viewed as peripheral, now appears central to the modern workplace experience.

Summary

This chapter explored the implications of the study's findings on how eco-anxiety affects employee engagement through psychological, organizational, and socio-environmental factors. Drawing on data from 182 participants, the chapter identifies actionable insights for professional practice, organizational leadership, and policy development.

Psychologically, cognitive dissonance, emotional exhaustion, chronic stress, and reduced well-being were significantly associated with lower engagement. These results suggest that eco-anxiety is more than a personal concern: it is a workplace condition that reduces emotional availability, motivation, and psychological presence. This highlights the need for managers to foster environments where environmental values and workplace realities are aligned, and where eco-anxiety is acknowledged as a legitimate psychosocial stressor.

At the organizational level, low engagement was strongly linked to the absence of sustainability initiatives, weak sustainability-oriented purpose statements, limited employee green behaviors, and a lack of proactive leadership on environmental initiatives. These findings underscore the role of culture and leadership in shaping perceived value congruence.

Sustainability appears to go beyond regulatory compliance and to be a core element of the organization's identity and culture. Employees are more likely to remain engaged when they perceive alignment between their values and their organization's mission.

Socio-environmental factors had meaningful implications. Media exposure to climate crises and perceived regulatory and market pressures negatively impacted engagement, indicating that external stressors can undermine focus and emotional stability. These effects underscore the importance of organizational sensemaking and resilience as mechanisms for mitigation.

Strategically, the concept of employee engagement should be redefined to reflect the realities of growing climate-related stress. Eco-anxiety emerges as a systemic issue with clear organizational and policy relevance. Its influence on employee engagement indicates its increasing relevance within contemporary workplace dynamics, including intersections with mental health and climate adaptation issues. Recognizing and addressing eco-anxiety is essential not only for cultivating a resilient, purpose-driven workforce but also for sustaining organizational performance and employee retention.

Chapter 6: Limitations and Recommendations for Future Research

This final chapter concludes the dissertation by reflecting on key findings, acknowledging the study's limitations, and outlining practical and scholarly pathways forward. The study's findings are limited by a Eurocentric, sector-specific sample that was predominantly female and composed largely of employees in sustainability-oriented roles within large organizations, which may restrict the generalizability of the results across different demographics, industries, and organizational contexts. The research was designed in response to a growing concern: the potential of eco-anxiety to undermine employee engagement in private companies. Guided by the problem statement—the negative impact of eco-anxiety on employee engagement—and grounded in Kahn's (1990) engagement theory, the transactional model of stress (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984), and the job demands-resources (JD-R) model (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007), this study sought to identify psychological, organizational, and socio-environmental factors that influence how eco-anxiety manifests in the workplace.

The purpose of the study was to quantitatively examine the relationship between eco-anxiety and employee engagement, using a non-experimental, cross-sectional design. Data were collected through an online questionnaire completed by 182 private-sector employees who reported experiencing eco-anxiety. Statistical analyses, including correlational and regression techniques, revealed several factors significantly associated with lower levels of employee engagement. These findings are synthesized in the eco-anxiety and workplace (dis)engagement (EWD) framework (Figure 3).

While this research offers valuable insights, it also has limitations. Methodological constraints, such as the use of self-reported data and the cross-sectional design, affect the

interpretation and generalizability of the results. These limitations also point to opportunities for future research.

The chapter begins by presenting actionable recommendations for organizational leaders and HR practitioners based on the study's findings. It then outlines directions for future academic research to further advance this emerging field at the intersection of environmental psychology and organizational behavior. The chapter concludes with a synthesis of the study's contributions and broader implications for building sustainable and psychologically supportive workplaces.

Recommendations for Practice

The findings of this study underscore the need for organizations to rethink how they approach employee engagement in the context of climate-related distress. Traditional models that focus on motivation, effort, and job satisfaction are increasingly inadequate for addressing the psychological complexities of eco-anxiety (Ahmed, 2019; Robertson & Cooper, 2010). This research contributes to an underexplored organizational challenge: declining employee engagement linked to climate change. It offers insights that advance both organizational behavior theory and the design of sustainable, psychologically supportive workplaces.

Building on the eco-anxiety and workplace (dis)engagement (EWD) framework developed in this study, this chapter recommends incorporating *employee resonance practices* as one practical avenue for applying the framework in management and HR strategies. Positioned as an aspect of broader organizational and psychological support, employee resonance practices can help address some of the key challenges identified in the EWD framework, particularly those related to fostering engagement, emotional well-being, and alignment between employee values and organizational purpose. To operationalize the EWD framework, this approach offers a

complementary set of practices that can enhance resilience and support employees as they navigate eco-anxiety and related stressors.

Grounded in empirical research and drawing on Kahn's (1990) engagement theory, the transactional model of stress (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984), and the JD-R model (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007), the EWD framework identifies three key areas where HR and management interventions can drive meaningful impact:

1. **Psychological factors:** Supporting employees in maintaining emotional and mental resilience in the face of eco-anxiety and climate-related stress, through fostering psychological coherence.
2. **Organizational factors:** Strengthening the alignment between employees' environmental values and the organization's sustainability efforts, through promoting organizational congruence.
3. **Socio-environmental factors:** Helping employees find and sustain a sense of purpose and meaning in their work, despite external pressures and pervasive climate narratives, through cultivating socio-environmental awareness.

The chosen employee resonance practices operationalize this framework, offering an integrated, systemic approach. The following sections detail how organizations can implement this strategy to foster alignment, meaning, and emotional resilience.

Embed Sustainability into Organizational Purpose

Employees reported higher engagement when their company's purpose explicitly included sustainability values (RQ7). This supports research showing that purpose-driven organizations create stronger emotional and ethical bonds with employees (Quinn & Thakor, 2018). To align with the EWD framework, companies could ensure that sustainability is

genuinely reflected in mission statements, corporate narratives, and strategic goals. Embedding this commitment in governance structures, such as through the company's bylaws, ensures it is more than symbolic. Such alignment reduces cognitive dissonance (RQ2), reinforces shared meaning, and helps employees navigate ecological stress with clarity and purpose.

Cultivate Environmentally Supportive Leadership

Employees who perceived their leaders as disengaged from environmental issues reported significantly lower engagement (RQ9). This aligns with research highlighting the importance of environmentally conscious leadership (Robertson & Barling, 2017). Leaders could actively model sustainable behaviors, communicate openly about environmental challenges and sustainability initiatives, and foster safe spaces for dialogue. This enhances organizational congruence and builds trust, helping to buffer the psychological strain of eco-anxiety.

Institutionalize Pro-Environmental Behaviors in Daily Practice

Both the absence of employee green behaviors (RQ8) and corporate sustainability initiatives (RQ6) were associated with lower engagement. Sustainability can be visibly enacted through daily routines, social norms, and peer modeling (Dumont et al., 2016; Ones & Dilchert, 2012). Organizations could encourage the formation of employee resource groups (ERGs), recognize environmental contributions, and embed eco-friendly practices into daily operations (e.g., implementing sustainable travel policies). Such initiatives foster psychological safety and strengthen employees' identification with the organization.

Provide Eco-Anxiety-Informed Mental Health Support

Findings confirm that emotional exhaustion (RQ3), chronic stress (RQ4), and reduced well-being (RQ5) from eco-anxiety undermine engagement. Addressing eco-anxiety requires tailored emotional support (Hickman et al., 2021; Pihkala, 2020). Organizations could

incorporate climate-aware mental health services into employee assistance programs (EAP), offer resilience workshops, and train managers to respond empathetically to climate-related concerns. This helps build psychological coherence and emotional resilience in the workplace.

Align Top-Down Communication with Bottom-Up Participation

Alignment between leadership messaging and employee empowerment in sustainability initiatives enhances engagement (RQ6–RQ9). To foster resonance, organizations must go beyond symbolic communication. They should create participatory channels for employees to co-design environmental policies and contribute to sustainability strategy (de Lange et al., 2022). This fosters a sense of agency and shared ownership.

Frame Environmental Uncertainty through Constructive Narrative

External signals, such as media coverage of climate crises (RQ10) and regulatory pressures (RQ12), impact workplace engagement. Employees bring these external climate-related emotions into the workplace. Organizations can help employees interpret environmental uncertainty as a call to action rather than a source of paralysis (Brulle & Norgaard, 2019; Pihkala, 2020). Tools such as Climate Fresks (Climate Fresk, 2025) and regular updates on climate-related regulatory impacts can support socio-environmental sensemaking, empowering employees to align with organizational goals and contribute to climate resilience.

Integrating Push/Pull Strategies to Support Employee Resonance

A balanced mix of *push* and *pull* environment-related mechanisms is central to the employee resonance strategy. Push strategies involve structured, organization-led initiatives (mandatory sustainability policies, climate-informed mental health support, resilience training, environmental literacy workshops). Pull strategies cultivate employee agency and cultural empowerment (grassroots initiatives, flexible sustainable choices, recognition of environmental

contributions). Together, these strategies foster psychological coherence, organizational congruence, and socio-environmental awareness. This balanced approach helps transform climate-related distress into sustained engagement and a positive return on investment.

In sum, these recommendations provide a practical and psychologically responsive pathway for organizations, in line with the eco-anxiety and workplace (dis)engagement (EWD) framework. By fostering psychological coherence, organizational congruence, and socio-environmental awareness, and by applying a balanced push/pull strategy, organizations can contribute to cultivating employee resonance. These insights directly address the study's purpose of identifying how eco-anxiety contributes to lowering employee engagement in private companies. They highlight that addressing eco-anxiety is not only essential for employee well-being but also for sustaining engagement and performance in organizations navigating environmental uncertainty. By integrating these findings, organizations can better understand and mitigate the disengaging effects of eco-anxiety while promoting a more adaptive and purposeful workforce.

Recommendations for Future Research

Building on the findings and contributions of this study, several avenues for future research emerge, both to refine the eco-anxiety and workplace (dis)engagement (EWD) framework and to evaluate the effectiveness of management strategies such as environmental employee resonance practices in organizational settings. As eco-anxiety becomes an increasingly salient feature of the workplace experience, further investigation is needed to understand its complex relationship with employee engagement, its variation across contexts, and how targeted HR interventions can mitigate its negative effects.

One key direction for future research involves the further development and empirical testing of the employee resonance strategy proposed here as a way to operationalize the EWD framework. Future studies could explore the effectiveness of specific interventions aligned with the environmental aspect of the resonance strategy and examine their impact on outcomes such as retention, well-being, and performance across different organizational contexts and cultures. In support of this, the exploratory use of Spearman's rho correlations in the present study revealed meaningful patterns that may reflect underlying constructs or latent dimensions of employee experience. Notably, emotional resilience and organizational integrity emerged as potential pathways linking eco-anxiety to engagement, suggesting internal consistency in how employee resonance functions. These findings provide a solid foundation for applying more advanced analytic strategies, such as exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and structural equation modeling (SEM). Future studies should use these techniques to empirically test the multifactorial structure of the EWD framework and examine its indirect effects on engagement. Longitudinal designs would further enrich this work by showing how resonance evolves in response to shifting environmental stressors or organizational interventions.

In addition to quantitative modeling, there is strong potential for qualitative research to deepen understanding of the EWD framework, particularly its emotional, cognitive, and value-laden dimensions. In-depth interviews or focus groups could capture how employees interpret and narrate their experiences of eco-anxiety, organizational support, and purpose alignment. Such methods would allow researchers to uncover the subjective meanings behind resonance-related behaviors and clarify the contextual and cultural factors that shape how this construct is lived in practice.

Another key area for future research concerns the moderating role of demographic and contextual factors in shaping how eco-anxiety affects engagement. The current findings indicate that variables such as age, gender, company size, region, and perceived organizational purpose significantly influence how eco-anxiety manifests in the workplace and how it impacts employee engagement. In contrast, industry and occupational specialization did not show consistent effects. These patterns suggest that future studies should incorporate demographic variability and workplace context into both study design and intervention strategies.

Methodologically, future research would benefit from addressing the limitations of this study. The sample was heavily Eurocentric and sector-specific, with over half of the participants drawn from sustainability-oriented roles. Additionally, the overrepresentation of women in the sample may have influenced the results, as prior research has shown gender differences in environmental concern and workplace engagement (Clayton & Karazsia, 2020; Coffey et al., 2021; Hickman et al., 2021; Niedzwiedz & Katikireddi, 2023). The high percentage of respondents working in organizations with a strong sustainability purpose and working in large organizations highlights the need to expand future samples to include populations with more diverse purpose alignment and lower environmental exposure.

Finally, while the EWD framework was developed in the specific context of climate change and eco-anxiety, its underlying principles, psychological coherence, organizational congruence, and socio-environmental awareness may also apply to other forms of systemic uncertainty. In an era increasingly defined by polycrisis, marked by the convergence of environmental, geopolitical, economic, and public health disruptions, future studies could explore whether employee resonance holds relevance across different types of global stressors (World Economic Forum, 2023). Understanding how employees remain engaged and purposeful

amidst overlapping crises, such as wars, trade conflicts, or social unrest, could extend the model's scope and offer critical insights for building workforce resilience in increasingly complex environments.

This study opens several promising pathways for advancing research at the intersection of environmental psychology, organizational behavior, and human resource management. By continuing to investigate and expand the concept of employee resonance to other contexts, researchers can support organizations in creating work environments that foster not only engagement but also meaning, adaptability, and psychological sustainability in a rapidly evolving world.

Conclusions

With the climate crisis intensifying and its psychological repercussions becoming more evident, this study addressed a critical yet underexplored issue in today's organizational landscape: the effect of eco-anxiety on employee engagement within the private sector. Using a quantitative, cross-sectional approach grounded in Kahn's engagement theory (1990), the transactional model of stress (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984), and the job demands-resources (JD-R) model (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007), the research identified key psychological, organizational, and socio-environmental factors that serve as proxies for eco-anxiety and contribute to reduced engagement levels.

Findings revealed that eco-anxiety undermines the fundamental conditions necessary for employee engagement. Psychological stressors, such as emotional exhaustion, diminished well-being, and a perceived lack of control, were strongly linked to disengagement. Organizational shortcomings, including weak sustainability initiatives, vague corporate purpose, and limited

leadership support, further eroded employees' sense of connection and motivation. External influences, such as climate-related media and regulatory uncertainty, compounded these effects.

A key practical contribution of this research is the development of the eco-anxiety and workplace (dis)engagement (EWD) framework, which helps to operationalize eco-anxiety disengagement in the workplace through employee resonance practices, a practical approach for HR and management. This strategy emphasizes aligning employee values with organizational purpose and ensuring that leadership, communication, and workplace culture visibly support sustainability goals. When such alignment is achieved, eco-anxiety can be reframed, not as a debilitating stressor, but as a motivator for commitment, purpose, and contribution. Without this resonance, however, organizations risk widespread disengagement or “quiet quitting.”

Importantly, eco-anxiety is not merely a personal issue: it is an organizational one. Leaders must recognize that addressing climate-related psychological stress is essential to sustaining employee well-being, motivation, and performance. This study provides a practical, evidence-based framework for creating supportive, environmentally conscious workplaces that foster both engagement and resilience. By embracing employee resonance strategies and authentically integrating environmental responsibility into their purpose, organizations can transform eco-anxiety into a driver of positive change. This not only strengthens retention and productivity but also deepens employees' sense of meaning, connection, and commitment at work in an era defined by environmental uncertainty.

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Appendices

Appendix A: Questionnaire

You are invited to participate in a research study examining factors that may indicate eco-anxiety and how these factors contribute to lower employee engagement in private sector organizations.

If you are 18 years or older, experiencing some level of eco-anxiety, and currently employed in a private company, please consider completing this questionnaire. Eco-anxiety refers to feelings of worry, fear, or helplessness about environmental issues such as climate change or ecological degradation.

Your insights are highly valuable and will contribute meaningfully to this research. If you consent to participate in this study, please proceed to complete the questionnaire.
Thank you for your participation.

Part A: Demographics

Question	Item	Options
D1.	<i>What is the number of employees in your organization?¹</i>	<input type="radio"/> Micro sized <10 <input type="radio"/> Small sized 10-49 <input type="radio"/> Medium sized 50-249 <input type="radio"/> Large sized 250+
D2.	<i>What is your occupation?</i>	<input type="radio"/> Open question
D3.	<i>In which sector or industry are you currently employed?</i>	<input type="radio"/> Open question
D4.	<i>Does the purpose of your company reflect a</i>	<input type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No

¹ The classification used in this questionnaire follows the enterprise size categories used by the European Commission, specifically the SME definition outlined in Recommendation 2003/361/EC. (https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/smes/sme-fundamentals/sme-definition_en)

	<i>commitment to environmental or social responsibility?</i> ²	
D5.	<i>What is your age group?</i> ³	<input type="radio"/> 24 and below <input type="radio"/> 25-54 <input type="radio"/> 55-64 <input type="radio"/> 65 and over
D6.	<i>What is your country of residence?</i>	<input type="radio"/> Open question
D7.	<i>What gender do you identify with?</i> ⁴	<input type="radio"/> Female <input type="radio"/> Male <input type="radio"/> Non-binary, or other <input type="radio"/> Prefer not to say

Justification: Demographic questions were included in this study to assess their potential impact on the measured outcomes. According to Harkiolakis (2021), these questions are essential for understanding participants' identities and ensuring their eligibility to complete the survey. Additionally, they play a key role in the data analysis process. The specific demographic factors chosen were informed by their relevance in prior research and aligned with the study's central research question (Abrahamse & Steg, 2009; Dumont et al., 2016; Niedzwiedz & Katikireddi, 2023).

² The question explores whether employees perceive their company's purpose as aligned with environmental or social responsibility. Research shows that such perceptions can positively influence employee engagement and provide a useful lens for interpreting the results (Glavas & Kelley, 2014; Good et al., 2021; Quinn & Thakor, 2018).

³ Age group classification follows the working-age population definitions provided by OECD. (https://www.oecd.org/en/data/indicators/employment-rate-by-age-group.html?utm_source=chatgpt.com)

⁴ Gender classification follows the UN recommendations to provide self-identified gender options beyond the male/female binary to reflect diverse gender identities. (<https://unsdg.un.org/sites/default/files/2022-03/UNDCO%20Gender%20Strategy%202021-2023.pdf>)

Part B: Subject Matter Question that Refers to Eco-anxiety

Questions	Item	Scale
<i>Q1.</i>	<i>I feel worried, fearful, or helpless about environmental issues such as climate change.</i>	Likert

Justification: To address the central research question (CRQ), participants' levels of eco-anxiety will be assessed with Q1 (Boluda-Verdú et al., 2022; Hickman et al., 2021; Hogg et al., 2024; Niedzwiedz & Katikireddi, 2023; Pihkala, 2020). Responses were solicited using a Likert-type scale, ranging from 1 to 7, representing "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree".

Part C: Subject Matter Question that Refers to the Employee Engagement

Questions	Item	Scale
<i>Q2.</i>	<i>I feel engaged in the work I do.</i>	Likert

Justification: To address the central research question (CRQ), participants' levels of engagement at work will be assessed with Q2 (Kahn, 1990; Macey & Schneider, 2008; Rich et al., 2010; Schaufeli et al., 2002). Responses were solicited using a Likert-type scale, ranging from 1 to 7, representing "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree".

Part D: Subject Matter Questions that Refer to the Psychological Factors (Hypotheses H1, H2, H3, H4, H5)

Question	Item	Scale

Q3.	<i>Feeling that I have little or no control over environmental issues lowers my engagement at work.</i>	Likert
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Justification: For RQ1 (H1), the question Q3 evaluates whether participants' perceived lack of control over ecological crises is linked to lower employee engagement (Hickman et al., 2021; Pihkala, 2020). This item reflects individuals' feelings of powerlessness in confronting environmental issues. Responses were solicited using a Likert-type scale, ranging from 1 to 7, representing "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree".

Question	Item	Scale
Q4.	<i>When I experience conflicts between my environmental values and my company's practices, it lowers my engagement at work.</i>	Likert

Justification: For RQ2 (H2), the question Q4 investigates the presence of cognitive dissonance, whether a mismatch between individuals' environmental values and their organization's behavior leads to psychological discomfort (Festinger, 1957; Gifford, 2011), which may in turn reduce employee engagement. Responses were solicited using a Likert-type scale, ranging from 1 to 7, representing "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree".

Question	Item	Scale
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Q5.	<i>Feeling emotionally exhausted due to eco-anxiety lowers my engagement at work.</i>	Likert
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Justification: For RQ3 (H3), the question Q5 examines the extent of emotional exhaustion caused by environmental concerns, which may reduce employees' emotional capacity to engage in their work (Jin et al., 2020; Pihkala, 2020). Responses were solicited using a Likert-type scale, ranging from 1 to 7, representing "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree".

Question	Item	Scale
Q6.	<i>When experiencing chronic stress related to climate change, it lowers my engagement at work.</i>	Likert

Justification: For RQ4 (H4), the question Q6 evaluates chronic stress resulting from ongoing exposure to climate threats. This prolonged stress can negatively affect mental health and job performance, ultimately reducing employee engagement (Hickman et al., 2021). Responses were solicited using a Likert-type scale, ranging from 1 to 7, representing "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree".

Question	Item	Scale
Q7.	<i>When my well-being is affected by concerns about the environment, it lowers my engagement at work.</i>	Likert

Justification: For RQ5 (H5), the question Q7 explores the association between diminished well-being and lower levels of employee engagement (World Health Organization, 2022; Pihkala, 2022b). Responses were solicited using a Likert-type scale, ranging from 1 to 7, representing "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree".

Part E: Subject Matter Questions that Refer to the Organizational Factors (Hypotheses H6, H7, H8, H9)

Question	Item	Scale
Q8.	<i>The lack of corporate sustainability initiatives in my organization lowers my engagement at work.</i>	Likert

Justification: For RQ6 (H6), the question Q8 investigates how employees perceive the presence or absence of corporate sustainability initiatives, which are key factors influencing employee engagement (Glavas & Kelley, 2014). A lack of such initiatives may signal organizational disengagement from environmental responsibility. Responses were solicited using a Likert-type scale, ranging from 1 to 7, representing "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree".

Question	Item	Scale
Q9.	<i>The lack of environmental or social responsibility in the purpose statement of my company lowers my engagement at work.</i>	Likert

Justification: For RQ7 (H7), the question Q9 evaluates whether the company's purpose aligns with sustainability values, which has been shown to enhance employees' sense of meaning and motivation at work (Good et al., 2021; Quinn & Thakor, 2018). Responses were solicited using a Likert-type scale, ranging from 1 to 7, representing "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree".

Question	Item	Scale
<i>Q10.</i>	<i>The absence of engagement in green behaviors within my organization lowers my engagement at work.</i>	Likert

Justification: For RQ8 (H8), the question Q10 captures employee green behaviors, which are essential for supporting organizational sustainability goals and can influence overall workplace engagement (Ones & Dilchert, 2012). Responses were solicited using a Likert-type scale, ranging from 1 to 7, representing "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree".

Question	Item	Scale
<i>Q11.</i>	<i>My organization's lack of leadership support for environmental issues lowers my engagement at work.</i>	Likert

Justification: For RQ9 (H9), the question Q11 assesses perceived leadership support for environmental issues, a key predictor of employee involvement in sustainability practices and

workplace engagement (Robertson & Barling, 2017). Responses were solicited using a Likert-type scale, ranging from 1 to 7, representing "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree".

Part F: Subject Matter Questions that Refer to the Socio-environmental Factors

(Hypotheses H10, H11, H12)

Question	Item	Scale
<i>Q12.</i>	<i>When the media presents climate crises, it lowers my engagement at work.</i>	Likert

Justification: For RQ10 (H10), the question Q12 explores the emotional and cognitive effects of media exposure to climate crises at work, which has been shown to elevate stress levels and affect psychological functioning (Niedzwiedz & Katikireddi, 2023). Responses were solicited using a Likert-type scale, ranging from 1 to 7, representing "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree".

Question	Item	Scale
<i>Q13.</i>	<i>Uncertainty about current and future environmental regulations lowers my engagement at work.</i>	Likert

Justification: For RQ11 (H11), the question Q13 addresses uncertainty regarding environmental regulations, which can reduce employees' concern and engagement by creating ambiguity in workplace expectations (Lu, 2024). Responses were solicited using a Likert-type scale, ranging from 1 to 7, representing "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree".

Question	Item	Scale
Q14.	<i>Growing pressure from regulations or market demands to act more sustainably lowers my engagement at work.</i>	Likert

Justification: For RQ12 (H12), the question Q14 evaluates the impact of perceived regulatory and market pressure, which can influence how organizations and employees engage with sustainability initiatives (Bansal & Roth, 2000). Responses were solicited using a Likert-type scale, ranging from 1 to 7, representing "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree".

Questionnaire Feedback Form

Thank you for completing the survey. Your feedback is invaluable in helping improve the quality and clarity of this research.

F1. How long did it take you to complete the questionnaire? ---

F2. Were any questions unclear, confusing, or difficult to answer?

No

Yes (please specify which questions and why): ---

F3. Based on the introduction, did the questionnaire match your expectations in terms of content and relevance?

The questions were more relevant than I expected

The questions were about what I expected

The questions were less relevant than I expected

F4. Do you feel that any important aspect was missing, considering the topic of the study?

No

Yes (please specify): ---

F5. (Optional) Would you like to receive a summary of the findings or be contacted for potential follow-up questions?

If so, please leave your email address: ---

Appendix B: French Questionnaire

Vous êtes invité(e) à participer à une étude de recherche examinant les facteurs pouvant indiquer de l'éco-anxiété et comment ces facteurs contribuent à une baisse de l'engagement des employés dans les entreprises du secteur privé.

Si vous avez 18 ans ou plus, que vous ressentez une certaine forme d'éco-anxiété et que vous travaillez actuellement dans une entreprise privée, veuillez envisager de remplir ce questionnaire.

L'éco-anxiété fait référence à des sentiments d'inquiétude, de peur ou d'impuissance face à des problèmes environnementaux tels que le changement climatique ou la dégradation écologique.

Vos réponses sont extrêmement précieuses et contribueront de manière significative à cette recherche. Si vous consentez à participer à cette étude, veuillez remplir le questionnaire.

Merci pour votre participation.

Partie A : Données démographiques

Question	Élément	Options
D1.	Quel est le nombre d'employés dans votre organisation ?	Micro-entreprise <10 Petite entreprise 10-49 Moyenne entreprise 50-249 Grande entreprise 250+
D2.	Quelle est votre profession ?	Question ouverte
D3.	Dans quel secteur ou industrie travaillez-vous actuellement ?	Question ouverte

D4.	La mission de votre entreprise reflète-t-elle un engagement responsable environnemental ou social ?	Oui Non
D5.	Quel est votre tranche d'âge ?	24 ans et moins 25-54 ans 55-64 ans 65 ans et plus
D6.	Quel est votre pays de résidence ?	Question ouverte
D7.	Quel est votre genre ?	Femme Homme Non-binaire ou autre Préfère ne pas répondre

Part B: Subject Matter Question that Refers to Eco-anxiety

Questions	Élément	Échelle
Q1.	Je me sens inquiet (ou inquiète), effrayé(e) ou impuissant(e) face aux problèmes environnementaux tels que le changement climatique.	Likert

Part C: Subject Matter Question that Refers to the Employee Engagement

Questions	Élément	Échelle
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Q2. Je me sens engagé(e) dans le travail que je fais. Likert

Part D: Subject Matter Questions that Refer to the Psychological Factors (Hypotheses H1, H2, H3, H4, H5)

Question	Élément	Échelle
Q3.	Le sentiment d'avoir peu ou aucun contrôle sur les problèmes environnementaux réduit mon engagement au travail.	Likert

Question	Élément	Échelle
Q4.	Lorsque je ressens des conflits entre mes valeurs environnementales et les pratiques de mon entreprise, cela réduit mon engagement au travail.	Likert

Question	Élément	Échelle
Q5.	Le sentiment d'épuisement émotionnel dû à l'éco-	Likert

	anxiété réduit mon engagement au travail.	
Question	Élément	Échelle
Q6.	Lorsque je ressens un stress chronique lié au changement climatique, cela réduit mon engagement au travail.	Likert

Question	Élément	Échelle
Q7.	Lorsque mon bien-être est affecté par des préoccupations environnementales, cela réduit mon engagement au travail.	Likert

Part E: Subject Matter Questions that Refer to the Organizational Factors (Hypotheses

H6, H7, H8, H9)

Question	Élément	Échelle
Q8.	Le manque d'initiatives de développement durable dans mon organisation	Likert

	réduit mon engagement au travail.	
Question	Élément	Échelle
Q9.	L'absence de responsabilité environnementale ou sociale dans la mission de mon entreprise réduit mon engagement au travail.	Likert
Question	Élément	Échelle
Q10.	L'absence d'engagement dans des comportements écologiques au sein de mon organisation réduit mon engagement au travail.	Likert
Question	Élément	Échelle
Q11.	Le manque de soutien de l'encadrement de mon organisation concernant les questions environnementales réduit mon engagement au travail.	Likert

Part F: Subject Matter Questions that Refer to the Socio-environmental Factors

(Hypotheses H10, H11, H12)

Question	Élément	Échelle
Q12.	Lorsque les médias présentent des crises climatiques, cela réduit mon engagement au travail.	Likert
Q13.	L'incertitude concernant les réglementations environnementales actuelles et futures réduit mon engagement au travail.	Likert
Q14.	La pression croissante des réglementations ou des exigences du marché pour agir de manière plus durable réduit mon engagement au travail.	Likert

Appendix C: Detailed Results

Case Processing Summary

Case Processing Summary

	Cases					
	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
FeelWorried	177	97.3%	5	2.7%	182	100.0%
FeelEngaged	177	97.3%	5	2.7%	182	100.0%
LittleControl	177	97.3%	5	2.7%	182	100.0%
ValueConflicts	177	97.3%	5	2.7%	182	100.0%
FeelExhausted	177	97.3%	5	2.7%	182	100.0%
StressLowersEngagement	177	97.3%	5	2.7%	182	100.0%
WellbeingTreat	177	97.3%	5	2.7%	182	100.0%
LackOfSustainability	177	97.3%	5	2.7%	182	100.0%
PurposeStatement	177	97.3%	5	2.7%	182	100.0%
AbsenseOfEngagement	177	97.3%	5	2.7%	182	100.0%
LackOfLeadership	177	97.3%	5	2.7%	182	100.0%
MediaPresentations	177	97.3%	5	2.7%	182	100.0%
Uncertainty	177	97.3%	5	2.7%	182	100.0%
Regularions	177	97.3%	5	2.7%	182	100.0%
NoEmployees	177	97.3%	5	2.7%	182	100.0%

Q-Q Plots and Boxplots

FeelWorried

FeelWorried - Normal Q-Q Plot - May 19, 2025

FeelWorried

FeelWorried - Boxplot - May 19, 2025

FeelWorried

FeelWorried - Detrended Normal Q-Q Plot - May 19, 2025

FeelEngaged

FeelEngaged - Normal Q-Q Plot - May 19, 2025

FeelEngaged

FeelEngaged - Boxplot - May 19, 2025

FeelEngaged

FeelEngaged - Detrended Normal Q-Q Plot - May 19, 2025

LittleControl

LittleControl - Detrended Normal Q-Q Plot - May 19, 2025

LittleControl

LittleControl - Normal Q-Q Plot - May 19, 2025

LittleControl

LittleControl - Boxplot - May 19, 2025

ValueConflicts

ValueConflicts - Normal Q-Q Plot - May 19, 2025

ValueConflicts

ValueConflicts - Detrended Normal Q-Q Plot - May 19, 2025

ValueConflicts

ValueConflicts - Normal Q-Q Plot - May 19, 2025

ValueConflicts

ValueConflicts - Boxplot - May 19, 2025

FeelExhausted

FeelExhausted - Boxplot - May 19, 2025

FeelExhausted

FeelExhausted - Detrended Normal Q-Q Plot - May 19, 2025

FeelExhausted

FeelExhausted - Normal Q-Q Plot - May 19, 2025

StressLowersEngagement

StressLowersEngagement - Normal Q-Q Plot - May 19, 2025

StressLowersEngagement

StressLowersEngagement - Boxplot - May 19, 2025

StressLowersEngagement

StressLowersEngagement - Detrended Normal Q-Q Plot - May 19, 2025

WellbeingTreat

WellbeingTreat - Normal Q-Q Plot - May 19, 2025

WellbeingTreat

WellbeingTreat - Boxplot - May 19, 2025

WellbeingTreat

WellbeingTreat - Detrended Normal Q-Q Plot - May 19, 2025

LackOfSustainability

LackOfSustainability - Normal Q-Q Plot - May 19, 2025

LackOfSustainability

LackOfSustainability - Boxplot - May 19, 2025

LackOfSustainability

LackOfSustainability - Detrended Normal Q-Q Plot - May 19, 2025

PurposeStatement

PurposeStatement - Normal Q-Q Plot - May 19, 2025

PurposeStatement

PurposeStatement - Boxplot - May 19, 2025

PurposeStatement

PurposeStatement - Detrended Normal Q-Q Plot - May 19, 2025

AbsenseOfEngagement

AbsenseOfEngagement - Normal Q-Q Plot - May 19, 2025

AbsenseOfEngagement

AbsenseOfEngagement - Boxplot - May 19, 2025

AbsenseOfEngagement

AbsenseOfEngagement - Detrended Normal Q-Q Plot - May 19, 2025

MediaPresentations

MediaPresentations - Normal Q-Q Plot - May 19, 2025

MediaPresentations

MediaPresentations - Boxplot - May 19, 2025

MediaPresentations

MediaPresentations - Detrended Normal Q-Q Plot - May 19, 2025

Uncertainty

Uncertainty - Normal Q-Q Plot - May 19, 2025

Uncertainty

Uncertainty - Boxplot - May 19, 2025

Uncertainty

Uncertainty - Detrended Normal Q-Q Plot - May 19, 2025

Regularions

Regularions - Normal Q-Q Plot - May 19, 2025

Regularions

Regularions - Boxplot - May 19, 2025

Regularions

Regularions - Detrended Normal Q-Q Plot - May 19, 2025

Frequency Tables

Frequency Table

Frequency Table - NoEmployees - May 19, 2025

NoEmployees					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Micro	2	1.1	1.1	1.1
	Small	3	1.6	1.7	2.8
	Medium	23	12.6	12.7	15.5
	Large	153	84.1	84.5	100.0
	Total	181	99.5	100.0	
Missing	System	1	.5		
Total		182	100.0		

Frequency Table

Frequency Table - Specialisation - May 19, 2025

Specialisation						
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	
Valid	Admin_HR	21	11.5	11.5	11.5	
	Analyst	31	17.0	17.0	28.6	
	Engineer	13	7.1	7.1	35.7	
	Finance	7	3.8	3.8	39.6	
	Marketing	6	3.3	3.3	42.9	
	Operations	7	3.8	3.8	46.7	
	Production	10	5.5	5.5	52.2	
	Sales	31	17.0	17.0	69.2	
	Other	56	30.8	30.8	100.0	
	Total		182	100.0	100.0	

Frequency Table

Frequency Table - Occupation - May 19, 2025

Occupation						
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	
Valid	Employee	104	57.1	57.1	57.1	
	Manager	41	22.5	22.5	79.7	
	Executive	8	4.4	4.4	84.1	
	Empty	29	15.9	15.9	100.0	
	Total		182	100.0	100.0	

Frequency Table

Frequency Table - Industry - May 19, 2025

Industry					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Sustainability	68	37.4	37.4	37.4
	ICT	44	24.2	24.2	61.5
	Energy	11	6.0	6.0	67.6
	Finance	7	3.8	3.8	71.4
	CCM	5	2.7	2.7	74.2
	Others	47	25.8	25.8	100.0
	Total		182	100.0	100.0

Frequency Table

Frequency Table - Region - May 19, 2025

Region					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Africa	29	15.9	15.9	15.9
	Asia-Pacific	14	7.7	7.7	23.6
	Europe	101	55.5	55.5	79.1
	North America	26	14.3	14.3	93.4
	South America	5	2.7	2.7	96.2
	Empty	7	3.8	3.8	100.0
	Total		182	100.0	100.0

Frequency Table

Frequency Table - Gender - May 19, 2025

Gender					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Female	131	72.0	72.0	72.0
	Male	42	23.1	23.1	95.1
	X	1	.5	.5	95.6
	NoAnswer	8	4.4	4.4	100.0
	Total		182	100.0	100.0

Frequency Table

Frequency Table - Age - May 19, 2025

Age						
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	
Valid	< 25	13	7.1	7.1	7.1	
	25-54	167	91.8	91.8	98.9	
	55-64	2	1.1	1.1	100.0	
	Total		182	100.0	100.0	

Frequency Table

Frequency Table - PurposeReflectCommitment - May 19, 2025

PurposeReflectCommitment					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No	24	13.2	13.3	13.3
	Yes	157	86.3	86.7	100.0
	Total		181	99.5	100.0
Missing	System	1	.5		
Total		182	100.0		

Frequencies

Frequencies - Statistics - May 19, 2025

Statistics									
		PurposeReflectCommitment	Age	Gender	Region	Industry	Occupation	Specialisation	NoEmployees
N	Valid	181	182	182	182	182	182	182	181
	Missing	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1

Tests of Normality

Explore - Tests of Normality - May 19, 2025

Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
FeelWorried	.400	177	.000	.617	177	.000
FeelEngaged	.292	177	.000	.811	177	.000
LittleControl	.197	177	.000	.926	177	.000
ValueConflicts	.201	177	.000	.855	177	.000
FeelExhausted	.200	177	.000	.926	177	.000
StressLowersEngagement	.187	177	.000	.928	177	.000
WellbeingTreat	.230	177	.000	.900	177	.000
LackOfSustainability	.178	177	.000	.881	177	.000
PurposeStatement	.186	177	.000	.895	177	.000
AbsenseOfEngagement	.198	177	.000	.882	177	.000
LackOfLeadership	.199	177	.000	.870	177	.000
MediaPresentations	.137	177	.000	.942	177	.000
Uncertainty	.198	177	.000	.927	177	.000
Regularions	.235	177	.000	.894	177	.000
NoEmployees	.498	177	.000	.434	177	.000

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Results from Wilcoxon Tests

Nonparametric Tests

Hypotheses Wilcoxon Tests - Hypothesis Test Summary - May 19, 2025

	Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision
1	The median of FeelWorried equals Neither.	One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test	.000	Reject the null hypothesis.
2	The median of FeelEngaged equals Neither.	One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test	.000	Reject the null hypothesis.
3	The median of LittleControl equals Neither.	One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test	.087	Retain the null hypothesis.
4	The median of ValueConflicts equals Neither.	One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test	.000	Reject the null hypothesis.
5	The median of FeelExhausted equals Neither.	One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test	.003	Reject the null hypothesis.
6	The median of StressLowersEngagement equals Neither.	One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test	.003	Reject the null hypothesis.
7	The median of WellbeingTreat equals Neither.	One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test	.000	Reject the null hypothesis.

8	The median of LackOfSustainability equals Neither.	One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test	.000	Reject the null hypothesis.
9	The median of PurposeStatement equals Neither.	One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test	.000	Reject the null hypothesis.
10	The median of AbsenseOfEngagement equals Neither.	One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test	.000	Reject the null hypothesis.
11	The median of LackOfLeadership equals Neither.	One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test	.000	Reject the null hypothesis.
12	The median of MediaPresentations equals Neither.	One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test	.020	Reject the null hypothesis.
13	The median of Uncertainty equals Neither.	One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test	.066	Retain the null hypothesis.
14	The median of Regularions equals Neither.	One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test	.000	Reject the null hypothesis.

Asymptotic significances are displayed. The significance level is .050.

FeelWorried

FeelWorried - One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test Summary - May 19, 2025

One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test Summary

Total N	182
Test Statistic	16653.000
Standard Error	685.991
Standardized Test Statistic	12.138
Asymptotic Sig. (2-sided test)	.000

FeelEngaged

FeelEngaged - One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test Summary - May 19, 2025

One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test Summary

Total N	181
Test Statistic	14619.000
Standard Error	650.476
Standardized Test Statistic	10.771
Asymptotic Sig. (2-sided test)	.000

FeelWorried

FeelWorried - One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test - May 19, 2025

FeelEngaged

FeelEngaged - One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test - May 19, 2025

ValueConflicts

ValueConflicts - One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test Summary - May 19, 2025

One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test Summary

Total N	182
Test Statistic	11801.000
Standard Error	589.540
Standardized Test Statistic	8.820
Asymptotic Sig. (2-sided test)	.000

LittleControl

LittleControl - One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test Summary - May 19, 2025

One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test Summary

Total N	182
Test Statistic	6894.500
Standard Error	542.285
Standardized Test Statistic	1.709
Asymptotic Sig. (2-sided test)	.087

ValueConflicts

ValueConflicts - One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test - May 19, 2025

LittleControl

LittleControl - One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test - May 19, 2025

FeelExhausted

FeelExhausted - One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test Summary - May 19, 2025

Total N	182
Test Statistic	7294.000
Standard Error	528.202
Standardized Test Statistic	2.946
Asymptotic Sig. (2-sided test)	.003

StressLowersEngagement

StressLowersEngagement - One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test Summary - May 19, 2025

Total N	182
Test Statistic	7471.000
Standard Error	538.650
Standardized Test Statistic	2.934
Asymptotic Sig. (2-sided test)	.003

FeelExhausted

FeelExhausted - One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test - May 19, 2025

StressLowersEngagement

StressLowersEngagement - One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test - May 19, 2025

WellbeingTreat

WellbeingTreat - One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test Summary - May 19, 2025

One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test Summary

Total N	182
Test Statistic	9655.000
Standard Error	597.617
Standardized Test Statistic	4.836
Asymptotic Sig. (2-sided test)	.000

LackOfSustainability

LackOfSustainability - One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test Summary - May 19, 2025

One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test Summary

Total N	182
Test Statistic	8806.500
Standard Error	556.998
Standardized Test Statistic	4.818
Asymptotic Sig. (2-sided test)	.000

WellbeingTreat

WellbeingTreat - One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test - May 19, 2025

LackOfSustainability

LackOfSustainability - One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test - May 19, 2025

PurposeStatement

PurposeStatement - One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test Summary - May 19, 2025

One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test Summary

Total N	181
Test Statistic	9142.000
Standard Error	567.477
Standardized Test Statistic	5.042
Asymptotic Sig. (2-sided test)	.000

AbsenseOfEngagement

AbsenseOfEngagement - One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test Summary - May 19, 2025

One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test Summary

Total N	182
Test Statistic	9718.500
Standard Error	594.534
Standardized Test Statistic	5.106
Asymptotic Sig. (2-sided test)	.000

PurposeStatement

PurposeStatement - One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test - May 19, 2025

AbsenseOfEngagement

AbsenseOfEngagement - One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test - May 19, 2025

LackOfLeadership

LackOfLeadership - One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test Summary - May 19, 2025

Total N	182
Test Statistic	9840.000
Standard Error	604.527
Standardized Test Statistic	4.950
Asymptotic Sig. (2-sided test)	.000

MediaPresentations

MediaPresentations - One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test Summary - May 19, 2025

Total N	181
Test Statistic	4257.000
Standard Error	506.483
Standardized Test Statistic	-2.334
Asymptotic Sig. (2-sided test)	.020

LackOfLeadership

LackOfLeadership - One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test - May 19, 2025

MediaPresentations

MediaPresentations - One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test - May 19, 2025

Uncertainty

Uncertainty - One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test Summary - May 19, 2025

One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test Summary

Total N	181
Test Statistic	6965.000
Standard Error	543.570
Standardized Test Statistic	1.835
Asymptotic Sig. (2-sided test)	.066

Regularions

Regularions - One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test Summary - May 19, 2025

One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test Summary

Total N	182
Test Statistic	1728.000
Standard Error	528.158
Standardized Test Statistic	-7.592
Asymptotic Sig. (2-sided test)	.000

Uncertainty

Uncertainty - One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test - May 19, 2025

Regularions

Regularions - One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test - May 19, 2025

